

MYRTUS

Multi-layer 360° dYnamic orchestration and interopeRable
design environmenT for compute-continUum Systems

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Acronyms

Acronym	Description
WLM	Workload Manager
DKB	Distributed Knowledge Base
NEM	Network Manager
NOM	Node Manager
MA	MIRTO Agent
P&SM	Privacy and Security Manager
MCA	MYRTUS Cloud Agent
MFA	MYRTUS Fog Agent
MEA	MYRTUS Edge Agent
DCOP	Distributed Constraint Optimization Problem
K8S	Kubernetes

Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the first version of the MIRTO Cognitive Engine architecture. The specification and first design version of the engine is completed. MYRTUS is already working on the initial implementation of this architecture. These advances represent a significant progress towards MYRTUS' primary goal of a multi-layer, interoperable, dynamic orchestration for compute-continuum systems. The MIRTO cognitive engine enables the orchestration (deployment and lifecycle management) of distributed applications across cloud, fog, and edge layers, seamlessly integrating them to enhance system responsiveness and sustainability. The relationships between our current development status and the MYRTUS' Pillar 2 proposed results and operational objectives are detailed in Appendix A.

The cognitive engine MIRTO has been designed to provide intelligent orchestration through continuous feedback, learning, and self-adaptation, thereby addressing the complex challenges posed by heterogeneous and geographically distributed resources.

In D5.1, the architecture is described in several aspects. We start with a description of the MIRTO structure, describing in detail its various components, their respective functionalities, and their relationships. We present the interfaces specified between the MIRTO components, and the interfaces towards the MYRTUS infrastructure (see Deliverable D3.1). We also present an Information Model that underlies the data formats and ontologies used for the communication between modules of the MIRTO engine. Finally, we discuss and exemplify how the MIRTO engine can be deployed in a multi-layered computing system and how the components work together for orchestrating applications in the continuum.

The architecture of the MIRTO cognitive engine is modular. It consists of the MIRTO Agent, Workload Manager, Node Manager, Network Manager, Privacy and Security Manager, Deployer, and Monitors. This modularity ensures transparency, flexibility, and ease of maintenance, as individual components can be replaced or updated without impacting the overall system.

MIRTO agents – in the core of the engine – provides a cognitive, distributed base for the orchestration work. Inside the MIRTO agents, key innovations presented include the Swarm-based workload manager, the DCOP-based workload manager, and DRL-based workload manager. Each of them offers unique optimization strategies suited to different system requirements. The Swarm-based WL Manager emphasizes scalability and adaptability, the DCOP-based WL Manager excels in handling complex interdependencies, and the DRL-based WL Manager focuses on long-term optimization through adaptive learning.

The Node Manager is responsible for optimizing FPGA-based edge nodes, leveraging machine learning models for workload characterization and resource management. Preliminary results have demonstrated significant improvements in resource efficiency and execution speed, validating the effectiveness of the proposed approach.

The Network Manager plays a critical role in monitoring and optimizing network performance, ensuring efficient communication across the continuum. By leveraging AI-driven decision-making, the Network Manager supports adaptive bandwidth allocation, enhancing overall system performance.

The Privacy and Security Manager ensures that security and privacy requirements are met, providing flexible and scalable security primitives that can adapt to changing requirements. The use of docker containers for security functionalities allows for easy replacement and updates, ensuring robustness and flexibility.

In conclusion, the MYRTUS project's MIRTO cognitive engine represents a significant advancement in the field of compute-continuum orchestration, offering innovative solutions to the challenges posed by heterogeneous and dynamic computing environments. The modular and intelligent design of the MIRTO cognitive engine, combined with its various managers and adaptive strategies, sets a strong foundation for future developments in this area.

TABLE 0.1: D5.1 DESCRIPTION FROM THE GRANT AGREEMENT.

D5.1 – MIRTO Cognitive Engine – v1

Architectural definition of the MIRTO cognitive engine and its managers. Stand-alone MIRTO agent implementation and assessment, partial integration, and detailed SoA analysis are discussed.

Tasks involved

T5.1(M3-M18) - Architecture and Integration [TNO (L), KCL, UNISS, UNICA, UPM, HIRO, LAKE, ABI, USI, ARK,CRF, TUD]

T5.2(M7-M18) - WL Manager [LAKE(L), TNO, ARK, KCL, HIRO].

T5.3(M7-M18) - Node Manager [UNISS(L), UPM, UNICA, ABI, KCL]

T5.4(M7-M18) - Network Manager [KCL (L), HIRO, ABI, TNO, ARK, CRF]

T5.5(M7-M18) - Privacy and Security Manager [USI (L), SOFT, UNISS, UNICA, UPM, HIRO, ABI, CRF, TNO]

1 Introduction

1.1 What is this document about?

This document presents the results of the work package 5 (WP5) of the MYRTUS project titled: ***MIRTO Cognitive Engine Release 1***.

The primary goals of WP5 is to design and implement the generic architecture of MIRTO runtime cognitive engine and release the initial version of platform-/device-/layer agnostic MIRTO managers that, all along the continuum, realise the envisioned “self-adaptive 360° orchestration” approach.

In MYRTUS an application is composed of several Software Components that work together to realize the objectives of the application. These Software Components form a network of services (a.k.a. Service Chain) that can exchange information via communication channels. Orchestration is defined as the task to assign Service Chain Components (and their corresponding Software Component implementation) to the ‘best fitted’ Compute Node (i.e. computing hardware) that is part of the MYRTUS infrastructure. These Compute Nodes can exist in the entire continuum: the cloud, the fog or on the edge.

MYRTUS primary challenge, embodied within WP5, is enabling orchestration of the continuum, which is necessary because today’s computing environments span very diverse and geographically distributed resources—ranging from resource-constrained edge devices to scalable but remotely located cloud infrastructures. Also applications’ components are distributed in the different environments to benefit from their strengths: computation heft and storage capabilities at clouds, and low latency, privacy, and energy efficiency at the edge. Thus, an orchestrated continuum—integrating edge, fog, and cloud—enables dynamic workload allocation and reallocation (when needed), near-zero latency when necessary, and overall enhanced system responsiveness and sustainability.

MYRTUS’s answer to the challenge of orchestration at the continuum is the cognitive engine MIRTO. The role of MIRTO is to provide the orchestration with intelligence through continuous feedback, learning, and self-adaptation. In Section 2.2.1, we present a short state-of-the-art review and discuss the advances that MIRTO provides.

1.2 KPIs driving MIRTO

Linking Service Chain Components / Software Components / Compute Nodes with each other has implications on several KPIs, such as the ***energy consumption*** at cloud/fog/edge, the ***networking costs*** between Software Components, the ***computation costs*** of Software Components, the ***calculation times*** of the Software Components etc. It is exactly these KPIs that are the drivers of the MYRTUS orchestration process. It should be emphasized that the architecture proposed does not restrict MYRTUS to use a limited set of KPIs / drivers. These KPIs can be defined at design time and are extensible. Note that the MIRTO Cognitive Engine includes several mechanisms for optimizing these KPIs in a holistic manner.

1.3 MYRTUS positioning with respect to the State of the Art

Novel approaches to design, deploy, and orchestrate a complex computing ecosystem, where a diversity of fog- and edge-level devices converge with the cloud to form a computing continuum, are yet to be defined. The European digital strategy places this technology as essential to “provide the trustworthy data processing infrastructure and services that public administrations, businesses and citizens require in Europe” [EUCo-2001]. Extreme digitalization and virtualization brought also unprecedented levels of computing pervasiveness and human-computer interaction. As examples, the smart factory 5.0 [Liu-2024], with cooperation of humans and cognitive machines, is coming soon. Likewise, the metaverse is expected to blur the boundaries between virtual and real worlds [Li-2024].

Centralized cloud orchestration is nowadays well-established [Bhavani-2014]. Variants of it extending to deployment at edge and IoT devices were in discussion already back in 2014 (see e.g. [Biswas-2024]). Decentralized orchestration solutions appeared next in many forms, such as *fog computing* [Skarlat-2016], *mobile-edge computing* [Ahmed-2016], *serverless computing* [Hellerstein-2018], but they are not established yet. There are many challenges provenient from the diversity of computing environments and their very heterogeneous resources. These challenges span from integrating the continuum, to programming it, and to its runtime management. This latter is where WP5 contributes. MYRTUS chooses an approach that emphasizes continuous feedback, learning, and self-adaptation to handle dynamic orchestration of workload and resources. This is the advance we aim at MYRTUS within WP5.

Workload allocation in the edge-fog-cloud continuum presents significant challenges due to the heterogeneous nature of resources and the varying computational capabilities across different layers [Shi-2016].

In recent years, several methods have addressed strategies for workload offloading in edge computing. For instance, federated learning was implemented to tackle the offloading problem in vehicular edge computing [Hasan-2024]. In another work, game theory was considered for task offloading in edge computing [Chen-2024]. Tong et al. [Tong-2020] proposed an adaptive task offloading and resource allocation algorithm for mobile edge computing environments, utilizing deep reinforcement learning to make offloading decisions and efficiently allocate computing resources. However, in the works mentioned above, the paradigms are considered isolated. To seamlessly integrate them as a continuum over all layers on the edge, fog, and cloud, analytical and hierarchical availability models were provided for the edge-fog-cloud computing continuum in [Pereira-2022]. Robles et al. [Robles-2024] proposed workload scheduling based on an adaptive container managed by Kubernetes for the continuum. It is noticeable that how to manage the edge-fog-cloud continuum more effectively is still a challenge for workload placement design [Gkonis-2023].

The decentralized orchestration strategy proposed in MYRTUS builds on a cognitive engine: MIRTO. MIRTO defines an architecture of distributed cognitive agents as a key enabler for managing heterogeneous resources at cloud, fog, and edge layers. By monitoring and modelling both the status of internal resources and external environmental cues, the cognitive engine can make informed decisions regarding resource allocation, task scheduling, and system reconfiguration. This intelligence is crucial not only for maintaining performance and energy efficiency, but also for ensuring security and trustworthiness across a diverse set of devices and administrative domains.

The MIRTO agent is motivated by several external factors stemming from the evolving landscape of distributed computing and the needs of modern applications. These factors include:

- **Increasing System Heterogeneity:** Applications now span from resource-constrained edge devices to powerful cloud infrastructures. This heterogeneity demands an intelligent mechanism to bridge these layers seamlessly.
- **Dynamic and Unpredictable Environments:** Real-world applications such as smart mobility, telemedicine, and autonomous systems operate in environments where conditions change rapidly—ranging from fluctuating network conditions to unexpected load variations. Moreover, the mobility and volatility of edge devices also face the issue of having dynamic topologies. All these changes require continuous real-time monitoring and adaptation to maintain performance, energy efficiency, and security.
- **Security, Privacy, and Trustworthiness:** With data being generated and processed at various points along the continuum, ensuring data protection and system security is critical. The MIRTO agent supports adaptive decision-making that can optimize not just performance, but also compliance with security and privacy requirements.
- **Evolving Scenarios:** Modern systems are dynamic so that all performance/power models eventually used to take decisions and manage workload and resources might rapidly become obsolete. Considering the adoption of Federated Learning strategies, the MIRTO cognitive engine will learn progressively from the incoming stream of data, retaining and integrating new information over time from distributed sources.

MYRTUS approach aligns with a fairly recent Intel's Open-Source Intent-Driven Orchestration (IDO) Framework¹. Unlike traditional orchestration methods that require explicit, low-level configuration directives, Intel's IDO allows administrators to specify high-level targets or "intents." Intent-driven deployment requests are based on users' indicated Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), such as required latency, throughput, or reliability targets, leaving it to the autonomous orchestration stack (based on Kubernetes) to determine what infrastructure resources will fulfill the objectives. MYRTO does something similar, largely leveraging Artificial Intelligence (AI) to realize high-level orchestration and then exploiting Ligo[Ligo-2025] and Kubernetes for low-level orchestration and deployment. In our case, four major orchestration/optimization drivers are considered:

- optimal workload execution (e.g. improving throughput and/or latency),
- optimal network usage (e.g. reducing network congestion, while guaranteeing adequate computing power),
- optimal node configuration (e.g. trading-off QoS to minimize energy consumption in specific components),
- privacy and security guarantees (e.g. changing the adopted set of components according to the requirements of a newly incoming task).

Indeed, besides being both based on a closed-loop approach, with respect to Intel's framework our manager-based approach (which will be presented in chapter 2) seem to cover a broader set of drives including privacy and security guarantees as well as energy among the considered KPIs. Indeed, energy efficiency isn't explicitly listed as a primary intent KPI in the foundational IDO model, even if Intel has explored integrating IDO with energy optimization tools, while on

¹ INTEL - <https://github.com/intel/intent-driven-orchestration>, [Accessed: 30/04/2025]

the security side there is no explicit mention of IDO utilizing security metrics as part of its orchestration objectives.

Also the NEPHELE European project² employs an intent-driven orchestration approach to manage distributed applications across the computing continuum, translating high-level objectives into actionable deployment and operational policies. In the NEPHELE case the following KPIs are considered for optimization: resource utilization, QoS compliance (such as latency and throughput), energy efficiency, scalability, and communication overhead. Indeed, again, privacy, security, and trust aspects are not among the considered goals and being the project still ongoing synergies and discussions can be established.

1.4 How is this document organized?

This document closely follows the structure of the organization of WP5. This resulted in the following chapters:

Chapter 3 (Task 5.1): Architecture and Integration, which defines the overall architecture, the main MIRTO components, the interfaces between components, and data / information model used in MIRTO.

Chapter 4 (Task 5.2): Workload (WL) manager, responsible for designing the mechanisms for orchestrating the Service Chain over the available compute nodes.

Chapter 5 (Task 5.3): Node manager, responsible for optimizing edge implementations of Software Components by configuring hardware accelerators for these components. Targeted hardware accelerators are FPGA and CGRA devices.

Chapter 6 (Task 5.4): Network manager, responsible for i) obtaining and sharing network related information, such as available communication channels and the corresponding communication bandwidths, and ii) facilitating changing the network settings on request of the WL manager. The network manager focuses on communication with edge services.

Chapter 7 (Task 5.5): Privacy and security (P&S) manager, responsible for monitoring if imposed requirements related to privacy and security are met, and configuring / updating P&S related primitives if necessary.

Chapter 8: Remarks and conclusions: Summarizing the most important findings related to the MIRTO Cognitive engine at the time of writing this document, and explaining the future steps to be taken.

We deliberately chose to write the main text of the deliverable in a dense way, leaving out technical details in the main text, aiming to realise a readable story minimizing the risk of technical information overload. The interested reader, however, can easily find the technical details in the appendices:

- Appendix A: List of the current status of all results of WP5

² NEPHELE - A lightweight software stack and synergetic meta-orchestration framework for the next generation compute continuum - <https://nephele-project.eu/>, [Accessed: 30/04/2025]

- Appendix B: Glossary
- Appendix C: ANT-Colony optimization
- Appendix D: DCOP problem formulation for the Workload Manager

Also, details can be found at the MIRTO Architecture web page, reachable via: <https://myrtus.hesi.energy>.

1.5 Related documents

D1.1 – UC Needs, requirements and KPIs v1. This document describes the use requirements as well as the technical requirements for the MYRTUS.

D3.1 - MIRTO Cognitive Engine v1. This documents defines the MYRTUS Reference Infrastructure for MYRTUS compliant computing continuum systems capable of supporting ubiquitous data collection and decentralized, intelligent decision-making.

D7.1 - MYRTUS DPE v1. This document describes MYRTUS tools and their extensions are described with their individual SoA analysis and preliminary advancements.

2 High level architecture

2.1 Introduction

MYRTUS offers a versatile solution for running services across the cloud-fog-edge continuum. It adapts its deployment and configuration based on the context and user requirements, ensuring flexibility and efficiency. When deploying a service-oriented application on MYRTUS-compliant computing continuum infrastructures, the operator should focus on the Service Chain Component definitions and its requirements, whilst the exact deployment details are optimized automatically by the system. This means that the operator doesn't need to worry about the specifics of where and how the services will run.

At the core of Service Chains deployment and orchestration is the MIRTO cognitive engine. This engine plays a crucial role in ensuring that users' services are executed at the appropriate nodes, remain operational throughout their lifecycle, and are cleaned up efficiently when they are no longer needed. The MIRTO cognitive engine is designed to optimize the deployment and operation of services, making sure they run smoothly and effectively.

The MIRTO cognitive engine itself is not a single, monolithic service, but instead is modular. It is composed of several services that interface with one another using well-defined REST interfaces. This modular design brings several advantages. Firstly, it makes the behaviour of the cognitive engine transparent and easy to understand. Secondly, it delegates responsibilities to services that isolate a specific function, which helps in a better system organization. Lastly, it allows for flexibility, as individual components can be replaced or updated if necessary, without affecting the functionality of the entire system, reducing the dependability on existing components and thus improving maintainability.

2.2 Taxonomy & structure

The MIRTO cognitive engine consists of the following core components, as depicted in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1 MIRTO component layout.

The blocks drawn in blue compose the core of the MIRTO Cognitive Engine. Helper blocks, relating to infrastructure components, are drawn in white (see also D3.1 for finding more information). They provide a standardized interface with MYRTUS computing continuum infrastructure, and ensure that the most up-to-date information is available.

1. **MIRTO Agent (MA):** The core MIRTO service responsible for coordinating and accessing all MIRTO managers. Also the primary access point for the MIRTO software specialist for installing, monitoring and troubleshooting applications.
2. **Workload Manager (WLM):** The brain of the cognitive engine that decides on which Software Components will be used to implement the Service Chain Components, as well as Software Component allocations (the Allocation Map). We will provide three different flavours of the workload manager that are based on:
 1. Swarm Intelligence – Biologically inspired optimization strategies are used in order to optimize software allocations, especially fit for large scale systems with relatively short lived services.
 2. Distributed Constraint Optimization Problems – Based on a collaborative multi-agent framework, making sure that connected Software Components are assigned to optimal resources.
 3. Deep Reinforcement Learning – AI models that are trained on historical data, provide software allocations to optimally use the available network infrastructure.

3. **Node Manager (NOM)**: Optimizes functionality of FPGA and CGRA-based edge nodes that might require specialized knowledge in order to effectively deploy and configure the Software Components over customizable computing nodes.
4. **Network Manager (NEM)**: Manages the network infrastructure, ensuring optimal bandwidth allocations when they are needed according to the requirements.
5. **Privacy and Security Manager (P&SM)**: Ensures that the correct privacy and security primitives are activated for meeting requirements related to privacy and security.
6. **Deployer**: Ensures that the Software Components are correctly deployed within the MYRTUS computing continuum infrastructure enabled by Ligo:
 1. **Ligo**[Ligo-2025] by seamlessly managing the cloud continuum lifecycle, enables the Deployer to dynamically see resources from cloud, fog, and edge layers to work and act as virtualized Kubernetes nodes. This dynamic approach minimizes complexity, enhances flexibility, and ensures a reliable, cross-layer solution
7. **Monitors**: Monitor the various subsystems of MYRTUS computing continuum infrastructure.
 1. Compute Node monitor – gathers information on the hardware running the different services.
 2. Network monitor – observes the status and performance of network infrastructure.
 3. Software Component monitor – keeps track of the desired and actual state of the Software Components of the applications.
8. **Workload characterization**: A specialized component that observes the behaviour of the Software Components to extract their actual behavior, that can be used for future decision making.
9. **Distributed knowledge base (DKB)**: A central database containing blobs of information and/or files, that any component might need for persisting or sharing of knowledge.
10. **Resource registry**: A specialized interface on top of the knowledge base to disseminate information on the status of the MYRTUS infrastructure.

2.3 Behaviour

The MIRTO cognitive engine consists of various interdependent components. The first component is the **MIRTO Agent**, a central entity that interconnects with all the other components. It is the component that an authorized user can interact with to start, update or stop an application, using a standardized interface, compatible with the TOSCA service specification³. The TOSCA file is parsed and translated into a MIRTO model of the Service Chain. The Service Chain consists of Service Chain Components that together realize the application. Together with a snapshot of the current system status, the service specification is sent to the Workload Manager to come up with an optimized deployment in the form of an Allocation Map, which maps Service Chain Components / Software Components / Compute Nodes.

The **Distributed Knowledge Base** serves as a central repository of information, containing data and files that any component might need for persisting or sharing knowledge. This shared resource ensures that all components have access to the information they need to function effectively.

³ OASIS Standard - [TOSCA Simple Profile in YAML Version 1.3](#), [Accessed: 30/04/2025]

The **Workload Manager** is the brain of the cognitive engine, responsible for deciding how Software Components are allocated across the available compute nodes. It receives instructions on new or updated service specifications from the MIRTO Agent, and uses some optimization strategy to come up with an optimal set of allocations in an allocation map. Different implementations of the Workload Manager share the same interface with the MIRTO Agent but vary in their optimization strategies and the information they require from the DKB. More information about the different Workload Managers can be found in Section 4.

To ensure optimal network performance, the **Network Manager** steps in. It continuously optimizes network throughput, bandwidth, and latency, ensuring that all components can utilize their allocated share of the network infrastructure effectively. In order to allocate bandwidth to Software Components, it communicates with the Workload Manager to ensure that decisions are made cooperatively.

Security and privacy are key aspects of the MYRTUS concept, and **Privacy and Security Manager** plays a key role here. It advises the Workload Manager on the necessary privacy and security measures, ensuring that all deployments adhere to the required standards. This collaboration ensures that the system remains secure and compliant with the privacy regulations, without compromising performance.

Once an optimal deployment is formulated, the MIRTO agent passes it to the **Deployer** to deploy the Software Components. The Deployer interacts with the underlying platform, powered by Ligo, acting as the standard interface to actually deploy the components independently of the level of compute resources: cloud, fog or edge. This ensures a smooth and efficient deployment process.

Ligo orchestrates the full lifecycle of workloads across the cloud continuum, spanning public cloud, fog, and edge environments, by abstracting and virtualizing available resources. It empowers the Deployer to utilize these distributed resources as fully functional Kubernetes nodes, regardless of their physical location or origin. The result is a unified, cross-layer Kubernetes infrastructure that adapts in real-time to shifting demands and resource availability.

The **Node Manager** focuses on optimizing the functionality of local nodes featuring hardware accelerators, such as FPGAs, or other specialized hardware. It works together with the Deployer to ensure that these specialized resources are utilized effectively, enhancing the system's overall performance.

Monitoring is a continuous process, and the Node, Network and Software **Monitors** keep an eye on the various subsystems of the MYRTUS platform. All relevant information on the system's state is stored in the DKB, ensuring that any component that relies on system information has the most up-to-date information, preserving historical data for analysis and training.

Finally, the **Resource Registry** acts as a specialized interface on top of the DKB. It distributes information on the current status of the MYRTUS system, providing a comprehensive view of resource availability and usage. This information is vital for the MIRTO Agent and other components to make informed decisions. As such, the Resource Registry contains the latest Compute Node status, Network status, and Software Component status information. All

information is also stored in the DKB, but only the latest version can be updated and retrieved through the Resource Registry.

Figure 2 MIRTO component sequence diagram, illustrating the sequence of data flow for deploying an application to the MYRTUS system.

Figure 2 illustrates the sequential operations of the MIRTO components when a software specialist is deploying a new application on the MYRTUS system using the API of the MIRTO agent. This will result in a cascade of operations by many components. In Figure 3 the control loop is depicted in which Monitors continuously update the system status, including the compute node status and software component status. Concurrently, the MIRTO agent continuously checks the system status to see if it still is functioning as intended. If not, it uses the workload manager and deployer to update the Software Component Allocations to comply with the requirements.

Figure 3 MIRTO sequence with continuous system monitoring loop. NEM, P&SM and NOM are omitted for simplicity.

2.4 Information model

The services that compose the MIRTO cognitive engine communicate with one another using well-defined REST interfaces. Data is shared with one another using the JSON data protocol, and the specific interfaces will be provided in the following sections. The common information model is represented in Figure 4a and 4b and discussed here.

Figure 4a: Information model Allocation Map

Figure 4b: Information model service chain

The MIRTO information model is heavily inspired by the Oasis TOSCA model. TOSCA is a standard for defining both hardware and software components of a system, and since it is an existing standard, there are already tools to work with. TOSCA is supported by other European projects, and as such, provides a starting point for defining our data model and terminology. However, there are certain design decisions and many details that we do not fully support, and as such we also define our own data model as depicted in Figure 4a and Figure 4b.

Recurring components in data model are the following:

- TOSCA Model: A CSAR file that defines the service specification using the TOSCA standard.
- Service Chain: The internal representation of the application to be deployed, as a set of chained services. It is composed of one or more Service Components.
- Service Chain Component: Describes individual services, with a name and at least one implementing Software Component, or multiple versions, for instance for different platforms.
- Service Chain Component Requirement: Specifies any requirement that applies to the Service Chain Component. This could be for instance a requirement to the maximum allowed latency, or whether the Service Chain Component *must* run in a specific layer (cloud/fog/edge). It is up to the workload manager to ensure these requirements are met.
- Software Component: Describes specific software implementations of a Service Chain Component, including their image URL and version.
- Software Component Requirements: Specifies the resource requirements for Software Components, such as CPU and RAM. Also the need for specific hardware accelerators when the application requires them.

- Software Component Characterization: Additional details of the Software Component behavior including the temporal behavior in terms of CPU and RAM utilization, also the performance/power consumption metrics in the case of using hardware accelerators.
- Software Component Status: The status of Software Components, including actual CPU and RAM usage, and the current state (created / running / stopped / failed).
- Infrastructure: Represents the infrastructure of the system, consisting of a set of Compute Nodes and connecting Networks.
- Compute Node: Describes compute resources, including its name and nominal CPU and RAM resources. Also the type and availability of hardware accelerators (FPGA-based or CGRA), if any.
- Network: Details network resources, including name, total bandwidth and latency.
- Compute Node Status: Provides information on available compute resources, including available CPU and RAM.
- Network Status: Contains information about actual network performance, including available bandwidth and actual latency.
- MIRTO System Status: Represents the overall status of the MIRTO system, consists of the Compute Node Status, Network Status and Software Component Status.
- Software Component Allocation: Defines the allocation of Software Components, mapping a Software Component to a Compute Node.
- Allocation Map: A collection of Software Allocations, including an allocation for every Software Component in a Service Chain.

2.5 Deployment of the MIRTO agent and MYRTUS sub-systems

This section outlines the various deployment configurations for the MYRTUS systems, focusing on the deployment of the MIRTO cognitive engine and the MYRTUS infrastructure within the computing continuum⁴.

The MIRTO architecture offers flexible deployment options to accommodate various operational requirements within the computing continuum. Deployment configurations differ from each other on the number and placement of agents, how resources in the continuum (compute nodes) are clustered, and the governance scope given to each agent. Below, we outline three typical, but not exhaustive, configurations: Centralized, Layer-Centric, and Redundant. Figures 5, 6, and 7 illustrate each of these configurations and are used along the text to explain deployment details.

Centralized Deployment

In a centralized setup, such as depicted in Figure 5, a single MIRTO cognitive engine is deployed on a server—such as a single desktop machine or cloud server. The single agent within the cognitive engine orchestrates applications across the continuum via a single Deployer System, which aggregates all K8S clusters (clusters of physical machines) as a virtual cluster. The advantage of the centralized configuration is simplicity. The agent offers a clear and single point of entry to the system (for users) and the orchestration decisions are taken all by a single agent that oversees all the computing resources.

⁴ The section does not cover the deployment of user applications; for information on that topic, please refer to the documentation in D9.1 Technology Assessment.

Independent of the deployment configuration, key components of a MIRTO cognitive engine (see Section 3.1) include: MIRTO agent, Workload (WLM) Manager, Network Manager (NEM), and Privacy and Security Manager (P&SM). Those modules are tightly coupled and deployed as one application **bundle** per instance of the MIRTO agent (only once at the first example).

Each agent is dependent on one Deployer, a Knowledge Base (KB) service point, and a Resource Registry (RR) service point. These services are deployed independently of the cognitive engine and should be available during deployment⁵. The Deployer service can reside on the same server as the MIRTO agent or elsewhere, like another cloud server. It communicates with Liqo virtual clusters which aggregate K8S clusters across various layers—cloud, fog, and edge. Edge nodes may be standard machines or edge accelerator clusters, which are specialized K8S clusters managed by a Node Manager to provide specific application deployment services. Node Managers are deployed inside each K8S edge accelerator cluster. Currently, accelerator clusters have only one machine, due to real-time requirements of the accelerators -- this is not a future restriction for the MIRTO architecture.

Typically, the Deployer service connects to the DKB to store resource information, making it accessible to the MIRTO agent via the RR service endpoint. Compute Nodes in each K8S cluster and accelerator clusters (currently equivalent to one Compute Node) may also have monitors linked to the DKB for system status and KPI monitoring. In this configuration, a single MIRTO agent handles orchestration requests sequentially, which may lead to delays under high demand.

⁵ Details on the function and deployment of other MYRTUS system components are available in D3.1

Figure 5 Centralized deployment configuration.

Layer-centric Deployment

The layer-centric configuration deploys one MIRTO agent per layer, each managing a subset of resources within the continuum. This approach provides users at various layers with their own entry points for orchestration and addresses situations where resource sharing is limited.

Resources controlled by each MIRTO agent are not confined to be in a single layer; for example, in Figure 6, the virtual cluster in the fog aggregates K8S clusters in both the fog and cloud layers. However, a particular MIRTO agent cannot directly deploy Software Components to resources not associated with its assigned Deployer.

In this setup, MIRTO agents communicate via their WL managers, enabling them to request deployment of parts of user applications on each other's resources. This inter-agent communication can introduce restrictions for deploying application components requiring internal communication, as network management does not extend between non-aggregated clusters.

Figure 6 Layer-Centric deployment configuration

Redundant Deployment

The redundant configuration (an example depicted in Figure 7) involves multiple MIRTO agents connected to the same Deployer, each deployed on separate machines—potentially across different layers. These agents serve as multiple entry points to the same set of services and resources, operating independently without the need for inter-agent communication or agreement on orchestration decisions.

This setup enhances system availability and resilience by allowing each MIRTO agent's WL managers (each agent has its own manager) to handle orchestration requests concurrently. If one agent becomes unavailable or busy, users can access another agent with the same resource set.

Deployment of the Knowledge Base and Resource Registry

For all MIRTO agents, information storage and management is provided by a unique DKB, encompassing resource information accessible via the RR service and KPI monitoring data used by various managers. The DKB is implemented as a distributed database, ensuring data consistency and availability across the system.

Access to the DKB is facilitated by service points, deployable at any layer, linking the DKB to users for data storage or retrieval. Due to its distributed nature, data stored elsewhere in the system is either periodically updated to resources behind each service point or fetched on demand when accessed.

Deployment decisions regarding the DKB and Resource Registry service points are made by the MYRTUS System Operator, considering factors such as security, redundancy, and performance. Various configurations are possible, including:

- Each layer having its own service points
- A single service point dedicated to a specific Deployer or K8S cluster
- Shared service points among all system components

Figure 7 Redundant deployment configuration

2.6 Conclusions and remarks

This section overviewed the basic structure and behavior of the MIRTO architecture. The MIRTO architecture is designed to make orchestration decisions across different layers of the continuum. The MIRTO agents are the core of the MYRTUS cognitive engine, providing the entry points and coordination for the deployment of Service Chains (applications). The section also describes how agents connect to the Distributed Knowledge Base, the Resource Registry, and the deployment layer. These three services support the orchestration process with overall system information, resource configuration and status in all layers, and actionable mechanisms to deploy Software Components in clusters at different layers.

The MIRTO architecture defines the orchestration behavior, determining a sequence of tasks to be performed by the Workload Manager, P&S Manager, and Network Manager. Their decisions result in an *Allocation Map*, a concrete set of configurations determining how the Service Chain components should be deployed and how the resources (security primitives and

network) should be configured. The MIRTO agents defer these instructions to a deployment layer, which in MYRTUS is based on Liqo and K8S clusters. The architecture definition included as well an information model that establishes the base for the communication between agents, managers, deployers, DKB, RR, etc.

Finally, we describe how the MIRTO agents, DKB, RR, deployers, and Node Managers can be deployed in the continuum. Here, there are many possibilities ranging from a centralized agent to a fully distributed system with several agents managing their partial resources, and redundant agents in place to guarantee availability of the orchestration infrastructure.

3 Workload manager

Edge computing enables data processing at the network's edge, utilizing IoT devices or local servers [Sat-2017]. This approach brings computation closer to the data source, resulting in faster response times and enhanced data security [Simic-2021]. However, edge devices have limited computing and storage capabilities compared to cloud servers. To address this limitation, fog computing serves as an intermediary layer, extending cloud services closer to edge devices and creating the edge-fog-cloud continuum.

Therefore, different alternatives are possible for deploying applications, each with their own implications. The main responsibility of the Workload Manager is to optimize the allocation of Service Chain Components (together forming the application) to Service Chain Components and Compute Nodes available in the MYRTUS Infrastructure.

Generally speaking, to optimize the edge-fog-cloud continuum, a workload manager should be able to [Ghasemi-2024]:

- Minimize latency: By processing data closer to its source, edge and fog computing reduce network latency, enabling real-time decision-making.
- Maximize resource utilization: Efficient allocation of resources across the continuum ensures optimal performance and cost-effectiveness.
- Balance processing load: Distributing workloads between edge, fog, and cloud layers helps prevent bottlenecks and improves overall system efficiency.
- Ensure data privacy and security: Local processing at the edge can enhance data privacy by reducing the need to transmit sensitive information to centralized servers.
- Adapt to network conditions: The manager should consider network bandwidth and connectivity to make intelligent placement decisions.

By addressing these factors, a workload manager can effectively leverage the strengths of each layer in the edge-fog-cloud continuum, optimizing performance, resource utilization, and user experience. Additionally to that, the WLM can orchestrate workloads with a strong emphasis on energy efficiency, ensuring that resource allocation and task execution align with the energy constraints of computing nodes while minimizing overall power consumption across the continuum.

3.1 Interface specification

Figure 8 Inputs and outputs of Workload Manager

The generic MIRTO Workload Manager (WLM) Interface depicted in the diagram is designed to dynamically manage and allocate Service Chain Components (e.g., microservices) across the edge-fog-cloud continuum. It achieves this by taking into account various inputs and system parameters to optimize resource utilization, latency, energy consumption, and cost. Below is a detailed description of its components:

Inputs to the Workload Manager

1. Service Chain

- Includes information about the incoming workload or microservices.
- Key parameters:
 - Input size: The size of the data required for processing.
 - Result size: The expected size of the output data.
 - Maximum latency requirement: The time constraint within which the task must be completed.

2. Compute Node Status

- Provides real-time data about the available resources on edge, fog, or cloud devices.
- Key parameters:
 - Available memory (MEM): The amount of free memory on a device.
 - Available CPU: The computational capacity currently available on the device.
 - Accelerator Flavour: The type of accelerator included in the edge/fog node, if any. MDC, CGRA or ARTICo3 are the options to be supported in MYRTUS. This is required to guarantee compatibility between the workload and the nodes available in the edge, in case accelerators are required.
 - Available Accelerator Resources: Depending on the accelerator flavour included in the node (if any), available resources will be expressed as #Slots and FPGA Type, for ARTICo3; Dimensions of the CGRA and Version ID (To ensure compatibility with the configuration format and supported operations), for the CGRA; and the version and Multi-threading support for MDC.

3. Network Status

- Offers insights into the network conditions that affect communication between devices in the continuum.
- Key parameter:
- Network cost estimation: A measure of network performance, such as bandwidth availability, latency, or energy cost associated with data transfer.

Outputs from the Workload Manager

- Allocation Map: Based on the inputs, the Workload Manager determines where each Service Chain Component should be deployed across edge, fog, or cloud layers to meet task requirements while optimizing for performance and resource constraints.

Integration with DKB

The Workload Manager interacts with a DKB, which stores system-wide parameters and historical data.

- Parameter Update: The Workload Manager updates the DKB with new information about resource usage, task execution metrics, and other system states.

This feedback loop ensures continuous learning and adaptation to changing conditions in real time.

In summary, this interface enables efficient workload scheduling by leveraging real-time task requirements, device-level resource availability, and network conditions while dynamically adapting through interaction with a knowledge base.

3.2 WL Manager Behaviour

3.2.1 Swarm-based WL Manager

Swarm intelligence, inspired by collective behaviors in nature like schools of fish and flocks of birds, operates through decentralized, self-organizing systems. In these systems, Swarming Agents follow local rules without centralized controllers, resulting in scalable, robust, and adaptive solutions. These characteristics make agent-based, swarm intelligence methods particularly well-suited for optimizing resource allocation and task distribution in the heterogeneous and dynamic edge-fog-cloud environment.

Key benefits of the agent-based swarm intelligence approach

- Scalability: The decentralized nature of swarm intelligence allows the system to scale efficiently as the number of devices and workloads increases.
- Adaptability: Swarming Agents can quickly respond to changes in resource availability, network conditions, and workload demands.
- Robustness: The system can continue functioning even if individual Swarming Agents fail or become unavailable.
- Optimized Resource Allocation: By considering multiple parameters, Swarming Agents can make intelligent decisions on where to process tasks, balancing factors such as latency, resource availability, and communication costs.

- Improved Efficiency: The collective behavior of Swarming Agents can lead to emergent optimization, potentially improving overall system performance and resource utilization.

By modeling the edge-fog-cloud continuum using this agent-based approach, our approach aims to demonstrate the potential of swarm intelligence in addressing the complex challenges of resource management and task distribution in modern distributed computing environments.

Description of swarming principle in the workload management

A workload manager for the edge-fog-cloud continuum performs a dynamic resource allocation (computing, storage) from the bottom-up where we deploy one swarm-based workload manager per compute node

- using the Service Chain Components as input,
- optimizing for factors such as latency, energy consumption, and cost
- while adapting to the heterogeneous and resource-constrained nature of edge devices.

For more details, the reader is referred to the Appendix, where the principle is described on the application of the ant algorithm.

The Swarming WLM proposes an innovative approach to modeling the edge-fog-cloud computing continuum using an agent-based system. This model consists of two primary types of Swarming Agents: resource swarming agents and demand swarming agents [Ghasemi-2024].

Resource agents represent the various computational nodes within the continuum, including edge devices, fog nodes, and cloud servers—the so-called MIRTO Agents each presenting a compute node. These agents are characterized by multiple parameters, such as available computational resources, communication costs, processing capabilities, geographic location, current workload, and energy consumption.

Demand agents, represented by Service Chain Components (e.g., microservices or pods as the smallest deployable units in Kubernetes), embody the workloads or tasks that require processing within the continuum. In this model, demand agents are responsible for determining the optimal resource agent for processing their workload, taking into account the various parameters associated with each resource agent.

The implementation of the Swarming Agents need to be finally decided for the specifics of the MYRTUS architecture and will be documented in D6.1.

SWOT Analysis

In summary, the Swarm-based WL Manager leverages swarm intelligence principles, inspired by natural collective behaviors, to dynamically allocate resources and distribute Service Chain Components across a heterogeneous edge-fog-cloud environment. Resource agents represent compute nodes and are treated as MIRTO Agents in the MYRTUS context, while demand agents autonomously seek optimal resources based on local rules and system parameters, optimizing for latency, energy consumption, and cost [WSG2025].

Table 3.1: SWOT Analyses Swarm-based WL Manager

<p>Strengths:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Distributed Problem Solving: Employs collective intelligence and parallel processing for more effective workload management compared to centralized approaches. ● Scalability: The local rules and interactions inherent in swarm intelligence enable the system to scale efficiently as the number of devices and workloads increases with reduced communication overhead. Communication limited to the neighborhood. ● Adaptability: Allows the system to dynamically adjust to changing network conditions, resource availability, and incoming workload types, enhancing resilience to node failures or network disruptions. ● Energy Efficiency: The lightweight resource allocation and reduced fog/cloud dependency contribute to lower energy consumption, aligning with the resource-constrained nature of edge devices. ● Optimized Resource Allocation: By considering multiple parameters (latency, resource availability, communication costs), demand agents can make intelligent decisions on where to process tasks, balancing various factors. ● Robustness: The decentralized approach enhances system robustness, allowing it to continue functioning effectively even if individual Swarming Agents fail or become unavailable. 	<p>Weaknesses:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Lack of Central Information: The distributed nature means no central information is available, which can make global optimization and system-wide monitoring more challenging. ● Deployment Complexity: Complex network structures can lead to significant deployment effort ("Swarming Agents" are potentially everywhere). ● Emergent Behavior Unpredictability: Swarm systems can exhibit emergent behaviors that are difficult to predict and control, potentially leading to unexpected or suboptimal workload allocation in certain scenarios. ● Parameter Tuning Challenges: Effective swarm behavior relies on carefully tuned parameters (e.g., pheromone deposit factor, evaporation rate). Finding the optimal parameter settings can be a complex and time-consuming process.
<p>Opportunities:</p>	<p>Threats:</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Integration with Existing Orchestration Platforms: Integrate with existing orchestration platforms like Kubernetes to facilitate deployment and management of microservices-based applications in the edge-fog-cloud continuum.● Enhanced Resource Utilization: Optimize resource utilization across the entire continuum by dynamically allocating workloads to underutilized resources.● Support for Diverse Workload Types: Adapt the swarm intelligence approach to effectively manage a wide range of workload types, including latency-sensitive applications, data analytics tasks, and AI inference workloads.● Development of Self-Tuning Mechanisms: Implement self-tuning mechanisms that automatically adjust swarm parameters based on real-time system conditions and performance metrics, reducing the need for manual configuration.● Exploration of Advanced Swarm Algorithms: Investigate and implement more advanced swarm intelligence algorithms (e.g., Particle Swarm Optimization, Artificial Bee Colony) to further enhance workload allocation performance.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Security Vulnerabilities: The distributed nature of swarm intelligence can create new security vulnerabilities, as malicious actors may attempt to compromise individual Swarming Agents or disrupt the swarm's collective behavior.● Competition from Alternative Workload Management Solutions: Face competition from existing workload management solutions, including centralized schedulers and other distributed approaches.● Complexity of the Edge-Fog-Cloud Environment: The inherent complexity of the edge-fog-cloud environment, with its heterogeneous devices, network conditions, and security constraints, can pose significant challenges to the successful deployment and operation of the swarm-based WL manager.● Lack of Standardization: The absence of widely accepted standards for edge computing and workload management can hinder interoperability and adoption of the swarm-based approach.
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3.2.2 DCOP WL manager

The role of a workload manager is to allocate Software Components to Compute Nodes, which is in essence a resource allocation problem. This closely matches the core of a Distributed Constraint Optimization Problem (DCOP), which is a mathematical problem formulation in which agents have to cooperatively assign values to variables, in order to minimize constraint costs between these variables. For the WLM, these constraint costs represent the communication latency, energy consumption or system load of running a Software Component

on a Compute Node. For a detailed description of how the WLM leverages DCOPs to find Allocation Maps, please see [Appendix D](#).

The DCOP based WLM uses a DCOP toolbox called SAM (Solvers with Agent-based Messaging), which hosts the multi-agent framework. In SAM the DCOP agents are merely a way to represent the different interests of Compute Nodes and Software Components, and do not relate to the MIRTO agents. SAM provides not only the means to describe the problem in terms of DCOPs, but also multiple algorithms for solving it.

The actual calculation of assignments, and retrieving the KPIs of hypothetical Software Component Allocations is done by DynAA. DynAA is a discrete event simulation environment, which models relations between entities by describing the events that can occur. Event handlers are triggered by such events, that make updates to the model, and trigger new events, thus defining a flow of activities. DynAA has the following properties that make it very suitable for computing system key performance indicators:

- Flexible: since the event based system is loosely coupled, the simulation environment is capable of dealing with dynamic addition or removal of components.
- Fast: a highly optimized simulation engine is capable of running simulations with very little overhead.
- Mixed level of detail: with user defined layers of implementation, a mixed level of granularities allows the system to model certain aspects in great detail, while keeping to basic interactions at other concepts. This mix allows the simulation environment to focus on the most relevant aspects.

The DynAA simulation engine provides a simulation environment that allows prediction of system performance. In order to calculate system KPIs, it needs the system description in terms of the compute and network resources, as well as the Software Component behaviour. To some extent, the models of the Software Components need to be provided during the development phase using the Distributed Knowledge Base. At a later stage, these models could also be determined automatically by the workload characterization modeller.

A schematic representation of the relation between SAM and DynAA in the WLM is presented in Figure 7.

Figure 9 The DCOP based WLM with SAM and DynAA internally communicating.

Optimization Criteria

The optimization criteria of the DCOP based WLM are mainly defined by the constraints, and their corresponding cost functions. The following criteria can be implemented, but which ones are used in the final system is a choice left for the system operator.

1. **Service Chain Component latency** - The predicted time between a software component receiving input, and sending the corresponding output. This depends mostly on the description of the Software Component, and the available resources on the Compute Node.
2. **Communication link latency** - The time between sending data, and receiving it at the other end. This is mostly dependent on the specifications of the Network, and how many different services will use it.
3. **Compute Node energy consumption** - The total energy consumption of a Compute Node is estimated for running its allocated Software Components, and running it for a certain estimated load. This criteria is a mix of several specifications, and will depend on a complex mix of Software Component Characterizations and Infrastructure specifications.

Note that by definition, all criteria are summed up for a total performance cost. This means a weighted cost should be made since not all criteria use the same unit.

SWOT Analysis of DCOP-based WL manager

Table 3.2: SWOT Analysis DCOP-based WL manager

<p>Strengths:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decisions are made in a distributed way, which avoids single-point of failure. Also, bad decisions can easily be adapted to, or recovered from. • Complex Service Chains with dependencies between Software Components are modelled as edges in graphs, and can naturally be described in the problem formulation. • Iterative algorithms can continuously run, taking into account latest information, which makes the assignment adapt to changing operating environments. 	<p>Weaknesses:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potentially many combinations must be calculated in order to find optimal solutions. This is especially problematic for situations with many compute nodes, and many dependencies between Software Components. This can be partially avoided by using sparse problem graphs, i.e. pruning the search space. • Not <i>*actual*</i> distribution of computation. Decision making agents run as different threads on the same CPU.
<p>Opportunities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pre-calculating component assignments during design time will increase computation speed. • Various algorithms exist that can be used in the same framework (i.e. CoCoA, DSA, MGM, Max-sum). 	<p>Threats:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Model simulation can become a bottleneck and slow down the optimization. • If the simulation environment does not match the production system, the optimized solution functions poorly.

3.2.3 DRL-based WL manager

The DRL-Based WLM is designed to jointly optimize workload placement and bandwidth allocation using DRL for making decisions across the compute continuum (Edge, Fog, Cloud) in a dynamic and resource-constrained environment. In MIRTO, each Service Chain is composed of a sequence of interdependent components. The allocation process for each component can be modeled as a sequential offloading problem, where the system must decide whether a Software Component should be executed locally (on the node where the request originates) or offloaded to another available Compute Node (e.g., Fog or Cloud). This formulation enables the DRL agent to consider both computing and network constraints in a unified decision-making framework. Specifically, it uses DRL to determine not only whether a Software Component should be executed locally or offloaded to a remote node, but also how much bandwidth should be allocated to support low-latency communication.

Optimization criteria

The objective is to improve the overall system performance by minimizing Software Component execution latency and ensuring efficient utilization of available infrastructure. The optimization criteria include:

- End-to-End Latency: The time required to execute a Software Component, including both computation and communication delays.
- Computational Resource Availability: The decision considers the current computational resource availability (CPU, memory, GPU).
- Communication Conditions: The decision also considers the current network status (channel conditions/latency/ bandwidth)

Description of DRL principle

Each Software Component Allocation can be treated as an offloading decision: the DRL WLM manager must decide whether to deploy it locally (on the node where the request is generated) or offload it to a more capable but possibly distant node (Fog or Cloud). This decision is affected by Software Component requirements such as maximum latency, and actual Compute and Network Status.

The DRL-Based WLM acts as an agent that continuously interacts with the MIRTO components. Its objective is to learn how to make effective real-time decisions for allocating Software Components as well as the network bandwidth based on the current system state. The DRL-WLM operates in a fully online manner, learning directly during deployment. Although performance may be suboptimal during the early stages—commonly known as the exploration phase—the agent gradually improves its policy over time. It does so by actively exploring different allocation strategies (referred to as actions in DRL) and adapting its decisions based on real-time feedback from system execution.

Specifically, these actions are selected by the DRL model based on the current MIRTO System Status, which includes available computing resources, network conditions, and the specific requirements of each Software Component. Over time, by observing the actual performance outcomes (such as execution delay), the DRL agent learns which decisions lead to better results. This allows the policy to continuously improve, making smarter choices that help reduce latency, and enhance overall system efficiency.

Specifically, for DRL-WLM Software Component Allocation, the following steps are required:

1. **State Observation**
At each decision step, the DRL-agent observes the MIRTO System Status, which includes: Real-time Network Status (e.g., bandwidth, latency, channel condition); Current Compute Node availability (e.g., CPU, memory, GPU); Software Component demands (e.g., resource needs, latency)
2. **Action Selection**
Based on the observed state, the agent uses its current policy to select an action, which consists of: Choosing the target Compute Node for deploying the Software Component; Allocating the appropriate network bandwidth for communication.
3. **System Execution and Feedback**
The chosen action is applied to the MIRTO system. The component is deployed, and the system monitors its actual performance, specifically the end-to-end execution latency.
4. **Reward Computation**
After deployment, a reward is computed based on the observed performance.

Typically, this is defined as the negative execution time, so that faster execution results in higher reward.

5. **Policy Update (Model Training)**

The interaction tuple—(state, action, reward, next state)—is used to improve the agent’s decision-making policy (model parameters). This enables the agent to self-evolve over time to have a better policy (a better model).

This real-time feedback loop allows the system to continuously adapt to dynamic workload patterns and infrastructure conditions, progressively improving the quality of Software Component allocation decisions.

SWOT Analysis of DRL-based WL manager

Table 3.3: SWOT Analysis DRL based WL manager

<p>Strengths:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Joint Optimization: Unlike the other WL Managers, the DRL-Based Workload Manager jointly optimizes workload offloading and bandwidth allocation, ensuring low-latency execution and efficient resource utilization. ● Global Optimization: DRL enables long-term learning, improving task placement efficiency and network usage over time. 	<p>Weaknesses:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● High Computational Cost: Training and deploying DRL models requires significant computational resources, making it more intensive than heuristic approaches. ● Cold Start Problem: The DRL model requires substantial training data before making optimal decisions, leading to suboptimal performance initially. ● Exploration vs. Exploitation Tradeoff: The learning phase may lead to temporary instability, impacting short-term performance. ● Complex Implementation: Integrating reinforcement learning, workload scheduling, and network optimization into a unified framework is more challenging than traditional workload managers.
<p>Opportunities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Improve Cold Start Performance: Use pre-trained models or imitation learning to initialize the DRL model with prior knowledge, reducing the time required to reach optimal decisions. ● Balance Exploration vs. Exploitation: Implement an adaptive exploration-exploitation strategy, where the model gradually shifts towards exploitation as performance stabilizes, reducing performance degradation in early phases. 	<p>Threats:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Training Overhead: The time and computational cost of training DRL models could make real-time optimization challenging. ● Mismatch Between Training & Deployment: If the training environment does not reflect real-world conditions, the DRL model may fail to generalize properly.

3.3 Conclusion and remarks

The choice between Swarm-, DCOP- and DRL-based WLM depends on system priorities, scalability requirements and operational constraints. Each approach is standing out in specific scenarios while facing limitations in others.

The Swarm-based WLM is to be used in a decentralized system that supports self-organizational concepts (e.g., ad-hoc and mobile networks), where additionally scalability across hundreds of agents can reach a performing system. Hence, energy efficiency and fault tolerance are top priorities. However, this approach should be not used if predictable behavior is required for critical applications due to the emergent behavior of the self-organized system approach.

The DCOP-based WLM is to be used if complex service chains with interdependencies dominate the workload (e.g., IoT pipelines with sequential processing). Additionally to that the DCOP-based WLM is very useful if you have incremental adjustments to node assignments instead of abrupt changes. However, if the overall system has distributed execution requirements (across physical computing nodes) and real-time reactive decision making is favored over optimization precision, the DCOP-based WLM is not the appropriate choice.

The DRL-based WLM is to be used when long-term optimization and adaptive learning are critical for the system requirements and the application require a joint optimization of latency-sensitive tasks and resource allocation. It is important to note that computational resources for training are available. However, if you need immediate deployment without training phases and therewith a stability during exploitation phase, the DRL-based WLM should not be used, even if the hardware would allow the intensive computation.

4 Node manager

The goal of the Node manager (NOM) is to provide runtime management of a local, accelerator Compute Node, focusing in particular on customizable FPGA-based Compute Nodes. As soon as the deployment on the software components on the node is complete, the Node Manager takes care of local node management from the hardware perspective selecting the optimal working point for the node given the input constraints. It also makes sure to maintain the execution as optimal as possible, reacting to local triggers and possibly changing from one working point to another at runtime.

4.1 Introduction

The runtime management of edge devices within the computing continuum has attracted significant attention due to the growing demand for low-latency, high-efficiency computing across distributed environments. Recent research has highlighted the growing complexity of managing runtime environments from the perspective of edge nodes in the edge-cloud continuum. Gkonis et al. [Gkonis-2023] emphasize how effective runtime management requires designing protocols and algorithms to support task offloading, resource allocation, and dynamic adaptation to network and computational changes. Santos et al. [Santos-2021] highlights the role of AI and machine learning in enabling autonomous runtime management. Di Nitto et al. [Di Nitto-2022] introduce the SODALITE approach, which focuses on automating

the deployment and operation of complex applications across heterogeneous environments, including edge devices. SODALITE proposes a model-driven approach where infrastructure-as-code is used to define deployment models, automate the provisioning of resources, and enable runtime reconfiguration based on real-time performance metrics. However, a computing continuum scenario raises another obstacle: the dynamic nature of workload requirements. While state-of-the-art solutions that target edge devices deal typically with static workloads where traditional ML suffice [Benzheng-2022, Makrani-2019], computing continuum devices face workloads with a dynamic nature introducing complexities that traditional, static models cannot effectively manage (e.e., run-time requirements, available computing resources, environmental or system changes). As an alternative, state-of-the-art approaches propose runtime management strategies based on data-driven models. These models are generated from online power and performance metrics collected during system operation, and they can adapt dynamically at runtime [Hadsell-2020]. While such approaches have been applied in high-performance computing scenarios [Tian-2023, Mirka-2020], they remain largely unexplored at the edge layer. This constitutes the research gap that MYRTUS addresses on this specific topic.

Principles of the Node Manager in MYRTUS

The NOM in MYRTUS performs local task execution optimizations in FPGA-based hardware accelerators mainly in terms of timing performance and power consumption. Its role is critical in simultaneously ensuring controllability and efficiency at the edge in continuum computing scenarios. The NOM leverages the FPGA's reconfigurability to deploy various hardware blocks like CGRA, RISC-V processors, and custom accelerators. These blocks enhance execution speed through hardware acceleration. Configuration affects FPGA resource usage, execution time, latency, and power consumption on edge devices.

The NOM maintains the system at its optimal operational point in accordance with execution constraints. It achieves this by performing local, machine learning-based runtime workload characterization focusing on power consumption and performance. This characterization is subsequently used to optimize workload execution. A specialized algorithm oversees the characterization process, ensuring models are kept up-to-date while minimizing training overhead, which is crucial for edge devices.

The ability to make configuration decisions directly at the edge avoids latencies due to the network. In fact, the state of the device at the edge may require immediate reconfiguration, or periodic reconfiguration with high frequency (e.g., due to battery discharge). Also, the amount of possible configurations for executing the required functionalities at the edge would burden deployment decisions with significant complexity. This is especially true in the case of the MYRTUS infrastructure, where devices at the edge integrate a heterogeneous FPGA-based hardware platform. The NOM involves integrating an Operating System (OS) and Kubernetes into the edge node, specifically on the CPU of its heterogeneous platform. These two modules are needed to provide orchestration on the FPGA die. The impact of this OS is minimized by using a custom lightweight Linux distribution, such as Yocto. This choice also reduces the size of containers, as they are isolated components based on the chosen distribution during generation.

Preliminary Results

We set up the OS on the AMD Kria K26 SoM. Preliminary results show that customizing an orchestration-oriented Linux distribution uses significantly fewer general-purpose hardware

resources—more than 70% less for CPU, 45% less for RAM in idle, and over 70% less for memory footprint—compared to vendor-provided Linux distributions.

Additionally, container orchestration improves efficiency. For the two evaluated computer vision applications, this leads to containers being reduced in size by over 80 percent and managed more quickly, with execution time reductions for creation and running ranging from 80 to 90 percent and 10 to 50 percent, respectively.

A preliminary version of ML-based models has been implemented on AMD Zynq UltraScale+ ZCU102 and Zynq 7000 Pynq-Z1 boards for run-time workload characterization. According to [Encinas-2025], the prediction accuracy is comparable to state-of-the-art modeling methodologies (continuous training), but using the proposed learning supervision algorithm, the overhead induced in the system due to the model training process is reduced around four times. The results are consistent across both boards, showing the portability necessary for compatibility among edge devices.

As a final remark, a proof-of-concept scheduling has also been tested. The preliminary results obtained on the AMD Zynq UltraScale+ ZCU102 board with a naive scheduler based on the run-time workload characterization showed workload execution time was reduced by 6.78% compared to a first-come, first-served approach. Furthermore, a software simulation using more complex scheduling policies (still based on the run-time workload characterization) has demonstrated a 25.96% workload execution time reduction.

4.2 Interface specification

Figure 10 Inputs and outputs of Node Manager

Table 4.1: Inputs and outputs of Node Manager

Data/Information	Type and Notes
Software Components	Input - Either a compiled SW binary or an equivalent container image - FPGA configuration bitstream (or its location)
Software Component Requirements	Input - Level of security - Optimization goal
Software Component Characterization	Output Knowledge from local models could be shared with the upper levels
Local Model Update	Local - Power consumption and performance traces are collected while tasks execute - ML models are locally updated on generated traces
Software Component Status	Output For each time instant of the execution process, NOM decides locally (on the host processor of SoC) among a set of possible hardware configurations of the accelerator (this accelerator can be constituted of parallel accelerating units of a multi-thread nature)

4.3 Behaviour

NOM is responsible for configuring the hardware of the FPGA-based edge device depending on the specific demands of the use case and the device's current state (see Figure 11 below). Part or all of the processing units (PUs) that are implementable on the FPGA (CGRA, RISC-V processor, and custom accelerators) must be used to execute Software Components that require hardware acceleration. In particular, these PUs are configurable. For example, CGRAs can be exploited to enable only some of the processing elements (PEs) of which they are composed, depending on the battery level. Through this configuration, NOM optimizes the execution of all tasks at the edge for timing and power consumption, determining when to execute each task to minimize conflicts and where to execute them to optimize FPGA logical resources. Additionally, the NOM includes a monitoring infrastructure that gathers run-time power consumption and performance traces during workload execution. These traces are fed to local ML-based models to perform a local run-time characterization of the workload, which

is then leveraged to make task scheduling decisions and workload execution optimization based on the execution requirements. Meanwhile, node KPIs are stored locally, together with the ML-based models, and can be transmitted to the Resource Registry and Knowledge Base databases, enabling supervision of data regarding the current values of KPIs.

Figure 11 Node Management

4.4 Performance & Power Consumption Modeling

The local run-time workload characterization relies on using data-driven ML-based models extracted at run-time. These models are used to predict power consumption and performance. To train these models, the monitoring infrastructure integrated into the NOM collects power and performance traces during workload execution. These traces are then processed at run time and fed into the models, which are incrementally trained as the workload executes. This incremental learning approach can introduce significant resource and execution overhead due to the need to continuously collect, process, and train traces. To avoid this, the learning process is managed by a supervisor that will be in charge of deciding whether or not to train the models based on the accuracy of their current predictions. Such an approach significantly reduces the modeling overhead by minimizing the time required to train the models, while ensuring that the models are kept up to date. Potential side effects (such as overfitting) that can occur during the training process have also been mitigated with this approach [Encinas-2025].

4.5 Conclusion and remarks

NOM makes it possible to have self-adaptive nodes, increasing the level of autonomy in managing devices at the edge. This distributed intelligence is required since applications are deployed, without an optimization-oriented strategy, through container orchestration (performed by Kubernetes) in a multi-cluster infrastructure with shared hardware resources

(thanks to Liqo). On the other hand, NOM can rely on machine learning models to continuously optimize execution in terms of timing and power consumption. Finally, the customization of the Linux-based distribution leads to significant advantages in resource efficiency and execution speed compared to pre-built environments, making this approach a more efficient choice for edge devices with limited resources.

5 Network manager

5.1 Introduction

The NEM plays a fundamental role in dynamically managing network resources across the compute continuum (edge, fog, and cloud), which are essential to support the Service Chain execution across distributed and heterogeneous computing environments.

In distributed computing environments such as MYRTUS, where Service Chain Components and Software Components are dynamically allocated to various Compute Nodes (e.g., edge, fog, and cloud), network performance is a crucial factor affecting overall system efficiency. Conventional static network management is insufficient to handle the rapidly changing workloads and connectivity demands across the continuum. In contrast, the NEM in MYRTUS continuously monitors and adjusts network resources based on real-time conditions, including available bandwidth, latency, and the communication requirements between distributed Software Components deployed across heterogeneous Compute Nodes. This adaptive approach is essential to achieving low-latency transmission, optimal resource utilization in a highly dynamic system.

A key responsibility of NEM is to inform the WLM (Swarm-Based WLM, DCOP-Based WLM, and DRL-Based WLM) about essential network state information. This information enables WLMs to perform network-aware scheduling and allocation of Software Components, and optimise task placement across the Compute Nodes based on current bandwidth, latency, and connectivity conditions. To support network-aware Software Components Allocation, the NEM is also responsible for estimating uplink and downlink transmission times between each two Computing Nodes, allocating bandwidth for communication between the Software Components. To achieve this, NEM leverages AI-driven decision-making, integrating DRL models to support the bandwidth allocations.

5.2 Interface specification

The NEM provides multiple APIs that facilitate seamless interaction between different MYRTUS components, ensuring efficient resource allocation, real-time network monitoring, and adaptive bandwidth optimization as shown in Figure 12. These interfaces allow the WLM and other MYRTUS services to query and adjust network parameters dynamically.

Figure 12 Inputs and outputs of Network Manager

Table 5.1: Inputs and outputs of Network Manager

Functionalities	Description	Input	Output
Get Network State	Request real-time network-related information, such as bandwidth utilisation and latency from DKB.	–	–
Transmission Latency Estimation	Estimates uplink and downlink transmission latency based on network conditions.	Source node, destination node, data size	Estimated latencies for data transmission
Bandwidth Allocation	Suggests bandwidth allocation values for active Software Components, taking into account current network state and specific requirements.	Input/output data size, computation latency, max latency constraints, current placement (source and destination nodes)	Bandwidth allocation

5.3 Behavior

Each API in the NEM is designed to support essential network functionalities enabling adaptive and efficient orchestration of Software Components across the MYRTUS infrastructure. Below is the expected behavior of the functions:

1. Network State Monitoring

- Periodically collects network data, including bandwidth usage, network latency, and other required/ necessary network information.
- Updates the Resource Registry with real-time network conditions.

2. Transmission Latency Estimation

To estimate how long it takes to send and receive data between two Compute Nodes.

- It checks the current network status and gives an estimate of the uplink and downlink latencies based on the input information including the source and destination node as well as the size of the transmitted data.
- If multiple Software Components are placed at the same time, the system uses a simple method (like averaging available bandwidth) to make a basic estimation.
- The estimated latency is sent back to the WLM, which uses it to decide where and how to place Software Components.

3. Bandwidth Allocation

- This API is used by the WLM who need to include the communication-related latency as well as the corresponding bandwidth allocation, which provides: the source and destination Compute Nodes; The size of input and output data and the latency requirements.
- The NEM checks current bandwidth availability across the path.
- It uses this information to suggest how much bandwidth could be used for this communication.
- The result is sent back to the WLM to support network-aware placement of the Software Component.

To explore adaptive and data-driven bandwidth allocation, the problem can be modeled as a DRL task, where the NEM acts as an intelligent DRL agent that continuously learns to improve bandwidth suggestions over time. By observing real-time network metrics and receiving feedback from system performance, the agent can iteratively optimize its policy to support more efficient and adaptive bandwidth allocation. The core DRL elements are mapped to the MYRTUS system as summarized in Table 6.2:

Table 5.2: List of the mapping between DRL system and MYRTUS system

DRL Elements	Mapping in MYRTUS System
Environment	Real-time network conditions, including bandwidth utilisation, latency, and placement decisions from the WLM.
Agent	The NEM, which aims to learn a policy to suggest bandwidth allocation decisions.
State	A simplified state vector such as: [bandwidth, estimated transmission time, input/output data size]
Action	Bandwidth suggestion for each active Software Component.
Reward	Optimized for: Minimizing task completion time (negative execution time as reward).
Policy	The DRL agent learns a policy to suggest the bandwidth allocation.

The DRL-based bandwidth allocation module follows a multi-phase training procedure to learn effective bandwidth allocation strategies for distributed Software Components.

1. Initialization:
 - Randomly initialize the bandwidth allocation strategy.
 - Begin experimenting with different bandwidth assignment scenarios.
2. Interactive Learning:
 - The NEM observes the current network conditions.
 - It selects a bandwidth allocation scheme.
 - Record the execution time.
 - Reward is calculated (e.g., shorter completion time → higher reward).
 - The DRL model adjusts the policy based on the received rewards.
3. Long-Term Optimization:
 - Over time, the model gradually learns a policy that improves allocation decisions.
 - The model continuously fine-tunes itself based on different Software Component Allocation and dynamic network conditions.
4. Deployment and Real-Time Decision Making:

- Once training is complete, the DRL model is deployed for real-time decision-making.
- Each time a new allocation request arrives, the NEM suggests the bandwidth allocation.

The interaction between the WLM and the NEM is essential for enabling network-aware Software Component allocation across the MYRTUS continuum. The coordination can be described in the following sequence as shown in Figure 13: When a user submits a request, it includes component-specific requirements such as input/output data size and latency constraints. These are received by the MIRTO Agent, which coordinates both the WLM and NEM. The NEM then estimates the wireless uplink transmission time (from the user to the fog) and the downlink transmission time (from fog back to the user). This latency estimation is sent to the WLM, which, in combination with available compute resources retrieved from the Resource Registry, determines the most suitable placement of Software Components across the fog and cloud nodes. Based on the resulting placement decisions, the NEM further provides bandwidth allocation suggestions to ensure efficient communication for each component execution.

Figure 13 Interaction WLM and NEM.

5.4 Conclusion and remarks

The NEM plays a key role in enabling network-aware Software Component orchestration within the MYRTUS continuum. It supports essential functionalities such as real-time network state monitoring, latency estimation, and bandwidth recommendation. Through its interaction with the WLM and the MIRTO Agent, the NEM facilitates informed scheduling and allocation decisions based on dynamic network conditions. The initial implementation of the NEM includes well-defined APIs based on OpenAPI 3.0 specifications, allowing for modular integration with other components of the MYRTUS architecture. In addition, a DRL-based bandwidth allocation algorithm is currently under-designed, aiming to provide adaptive, data-driven suggestions for improving communication efficiency over time.

6 Privacy and security manager

6.1 Introduction

The privacy and security manager is responsible for all security functionalities in MYRTUS and for ensuring that the security requirements are constantly respected at runtime, even in presence of changes. In a nutshell, it is aware of which security functionality can be provided by a software component, of the security requirements, and receives information for computing the trust level. As output it produces a recommendation to the WLM on the security primitive to be executed.

The security functionalities are provided by means of the security primitives that are developed in WP3 and synthesized in WP7. At the moment, we provide primitives for four security functionalities (see Table 7.1): Encryption, Hashing, Digital Signature, Key Exchange Mechanism. Nevertheless, the security manager and the way in which each functionality is provided is general, and can be easily extended to support other functionalities, for instance, to other privacy preserving features, that will be added to the manager in the second phase of the project. The primitives implementing the functionalities will be made available over a range of implementation styles, platforms and architectures. As presented in Deliverable D3.1, for each functionality, we provide primitives guaranteeing three distinct security levels: low, medium and high. We summarize here the meaning of each level. The security level High is intended to cater for use cases where high security is required, such as context where quantum resistance is required by the underlying application (in that case, Post Quantum Secure algorithms will be used and enforced). However, high security levels also need higher computational resources or power, which might not be available in all the platforms used in MYRTUS. On the other hand, the Low security level typically relies on lightweight algorithms where low power/energy consumption is of more relevance to the application. These algorithms have, as the name says, a reduced usage of resources, but often do not ensure strong security such as quantum resistance. The medium level lies in between these: that offers a higher security than low level, with a moderate computational workload. In addition to the use of different security primitives, changes in performance and resource usage can come from different implementation strategies of the same algorithm. In fact, each implementation achieves different performance and may require a different number of clock cycles or energy to execute, even on the same platforms. The manager will also keep track of this to drive the decision on the security primitives to be executed.

As mentioned, the overall task of the security manager is ensure that the security and privacy requirements are always met during the execution of the application. To ensure that, it reacts to requests for each of the security tasks. The requests, that are performed via the interface specified in the next section, includes, at minimum, the required security level, but can also include more details, such as the specific selection and the configuration of the needed privacy and security primitives, explicitly requested of specific implementation of the security primitive or a certain throughput or energy requirement. The manager uses all the information in the request, is aware of the security primitives available on a given node, and returns the recommendation for instantiating the most appropriate executable to perform the task on a given node.

As mentioned, the minimal selection that has to be done in the request is the one of the security level. The security level of each primitive is defined when the primitive is added to the pool of existing primitives, and propagated to all the relevant recipients systemwide. It is also

noteworthy to mention that the definition of security level may change at any given point of time. For example, in the unlikely event that AES-256 is found to be no longer secure in the post quantum setting, the security manager will be able to adapt the security level of AES-256. Also, when available, a novel and quantum resistant primitive could be immediately added to the system.

6.2 Interface specification

The Security Manager provides APIs that facilitate security related tasks inside of MYRTUS. The interface is organized as specified in Fig 7.1. Given security and performance requirements, it takes into account device level information and trust parameters etc to make a recommendation of the security primitive to be used for the task and on which node the task should be executed.

Figure 14 Security and privacy interface.

Table 6.1: Inputs and outputs of Security and privacy manager.

Interface	Description	Input	Output
Requirements API	Specification of the security requirements and of the optional requirements on the security primitive, such as target performance and energy	Mandatory inputs: Security level (high, medium, low) Optional Inputs: Target Energy Target Performance	Recommended security primitive and command line to execute it; security level of the selected primitive

Device-level information API	Information about the computational power and energy budget of a specific node	Power consumption, energy available, and computational power of node	none
Information to assess trust API			Updated Trust Level

6.3 Behaviour

As mentioned, the P&S manager has to react to security requests that can be generated for various reasons. Certainly, a change in the allocation of the computation would lead to a new request for the P&S manager, since it has to assess if the security requirements are still met and could have to generate a new recommendation. Similarly, a change in the resource available (such as energy) could lead to a need of changing the executed security primitive with another that consumes less energy (for instance, and high throughput implementation of the AES algorithm vs a low energy but low throughput one). Finally, the security requirements might change. Also in this case, the S&P Manager should issue a new recommendation. To test the functionalities of the Privacy and Security Manager and to ensure that we can react to all these requests, we have implemented a preliminary version of it as a Docker container that reacts to network requests. The information needed to create the network request are extracted from the APIs described above. In this phase of development, a number of synthetic request has been created mimicking the requests that will come during normal operation described above. Currently, the Security Manager runs as a docker container that has access to the binary executable of each of the security primitives. The available primitives are currently implemented as software only but for certain primitives an hardware implementation will be provided too.

In the current test version, the P&S manager listens to the synthetic requests that are mimicking the request coming from the MYRTO agents and from the WL manager. The manager would parse the request, to determine the specific nature of the request, and any other performance related commands specified in it. For example the WL manager may request encryption of video files captured by traffic cameras with high throughput and high security level, for use during peak traffic hours. The P&S manager then uses its underlying logic to make a recommendation of the module that would execute the given operation, i.e. it suggests the path of the executable and commands needed to execute it. The action of selecting the primitive to finalize the recommendation is similar to the way in which the primitives are synthesized (described in deliverable D7.1). However, in the case of the manager, this decision is carried out at run time.

In addition to the P&R Manager that is implemented as docker, at the moment, each security functionality is implemented as a separate docker. Information on these dockers are maintained by the P&S manager, together with information on the nodes where they can be executed. The docker of each security functionality stores the software implementation of all the cryptographic primitives selected during synthesis. These can be different implementations

of the same primitives (for instance, an implementation of AES 128 that uses dedicated instructions, an implementation of AES 128 based on bitslicing) or implementation of different primitives (for instance AES 128, AES 256, PRESENT). The manager, by parsing the requests, will take care of selecting a cryptographic primitive that adheres to the security requirements and generates a suggestion for the WLM on the primitives to be executed. The suggestion takes the form of the command line to execute the selected primitives. As mentioned, hardware implementation of security primitives is not implemented yet. However, where hardware implementation will be provided, we foresee using an FPGA device as target for the hardware. In this case we plan to give the container access to the bitstream corresponding to the needed security primitive which can be offloaded to the FPGA fabric. In this case the docker also has access to the communication interface with the FPGA.

Runtime Changes

Fig 7.1 gives an overview of the Privacy and Security Manager implemented as a docker container. As mentioned, to test the functionalities, it currently reacts to network requests mimicking the request that will come from MYRTUS agents and WLM. Tests with real requests will happen in the following months of the project. At the moment, the managers performs the following tasks

1. It listens for incoming synthetic requests for security related tasks. The synthetic requests are generated for test purposes and cover a large spectrum of possible changes that can happen at runtime. At the moment, supported requests are encryption, hashing, digital signature or key exchange.
2. It queues and parses all such requests
3. Consulting the library of available components selects firstly the docker containers providing the requested security functionality, then selects the exact primitives to be executed according to the performance/security level desired
4. If the selected primitive is available in the target node, the P&S Manager converts the selection carried out in point 3 into a recommendation for the WLM. The recommendation takes the form of the command line arguments to be used to execute the security primitive on a specific software component.
5. In case the selected primitive is not available in the node, it may occur that Software Components that perform the security tasks need to be modified at runtime. This can happen for various reasons like specific algorithm are requested by applications (for instance, an application requires an ISO certification, thus the PRESENT algorithm must be used) or simply because the target node does not support a specific primitive. In this case, the S&P manager can react in two ways. If the selected primitive is not available on the node, but is available on the library, where possible, the selected primitive will be added to the Software Component. Once the addition of the primitive is completed, the S&P Manager will forward the related suggestion to the WL manager. Otherwise the S&P Manger will inform the WL manager that the service is not available and that the security requirements, with this request, can not be met. In that case the WL manager simply assigns the task to another node. Figure 15 summarizes the behaviour of the current S&P Manager.

Security and Privacy Manager

Figure 15 Sequence diagram for top level Security and Privacy manager

6.4 Conclusion and remarks

The Security and Privacy Manager is a fundamental block of the MYRTUS environment and infrastructure. It ensures that the security and privacy requirements are met and provides to the workload manager all the information needed to deploy the computation on the agents. In a nutshell, it takes a request for a security functionality, that can be as generic as the functionality itself and the required level of security, and returns the recommendation to the WLM of the security primitive to be executed, currently in the form of a command line to instantiate and execute a cryptographic primitive implementing that functionality within a docker container. The initial implementation supports four security functionalities. Support for other security functionalities and hardware implementation of security primitive is still under development.

7 Conclusions and future work

7.1 Operational objectives

WP5, and Pillar 2 development, is progressing as expected.

Originally five different Operational Objectives (OOs) were planned. These OOs and how the development in this first half of the project are contributing to reaching them are summarized below.

Table 7.1 Updates on operational objectives.

T2.OO.a - Formalization of a generic multi-layer cognitive self-adaptation engine constituted of different resource- and layer- specific agents, implementing customised management.

The architecture of MIRTO is described in several aspects. We start with a description of the MIRTO structure, describing in detail its various components, their respective functionalities, and their relationships. We present the interfaces specified between the MIRTO components, and the interfaces towards the MYRTUS Reference Infrastructure (see Deliverable D3.1). Drivers for runtime reconfiguration and optimization (optimal workload execution, optimal network usage, optimal node configuration, and privacy and security guarantees) have been thoroughly discussed and mapped to the different managers of MIRTO architecture. We also present an Information Model that underlies the data formats and ontologies used for the communication between modules of the MIRTO engine.

See also updates on the following results in appendix A:

R6, R7, R8, R9 R10, R11, R12, R13, R14, R17

T2.OO.b - Definition of novel AI-powered management strategies and libraries of orchestration algorithms, based on SI and FL methodologies, to provide 360° orchestration of resources/tasks/services/security aspects.

MIRTO agents – in the core of the engine – provides a cognitive, distributed base for the orchestration work. Inside the MIRTO agents, key innovations presented include the Swarm-based workload manager, the DCOP-based workload manager, and DRL-based workload manager. Each of them offering unique optimization strategies suited to different system requirements. The Swarm-based WL Manager emphasizes scalability and adaptability, the DCOP-based WL Manager excels in handling complex interdependencies, and the DRL-based WL Manager focuses on long-term optimization through adaptive learning. Federated

Learning strategies are going to be used also to improve the communication efficiency by the joint use of the DRL-based WL Manager and the Network Manager.

See also updates on the following results in appendix A:

R8, R9 R10, R11, R12, R13, R17

T2.OO.c – Definition of different AI models for WL characterization at deployment/runtime time.

The Node Manager is expected to be able to decide, autonomously and based on AI models derived from workload characterization, about the workpoint activation of co-processing units. The actual characterization of different WL types over edge devices is progressing. All the monitoring support to gather the execution data to derive the models has been already developed within Pillar 1 and there are already some preliminary models available for FPGA-based edge devices.

See also updates on the following results in appendix A:

R6, R11

T2.OO.d - Definition of an AI-based optimization module capable of re-engineering part incoming WLS to make them more performing while running on the computing continuum.

The orchestration problem to be solved using SAM will consider the possibility of using different service implementations to compose or select dynamically the system composition to be used. Different service chains will be considered and selected according to their performance indicators during runtime. Additionally, this OO is linked to an activity, the use of Large Language Models to optimize a given WL (R7), which is planned in WP6.

See also updates on the following results in appendix A:

R7, R10, R17

T2.OO.e - Support legacy systems leveraging on widely adopted technologies, such as TOSCA and Kubernetes.

The envisioned cloud-fog-edge virtualization techniques will facilitate low-level orchestration of the continuum, supporting also Kubernetes integration with legacy systems when applicable. All nodes connected within the MYRTUS Reference Infrastructure are already supporting Kubernetes (see D3.1) as low-level orchestrator and use LIQO to establish the continuum. LIQO is Kubernetes-based which is a standard de-facto for resource orchestration in cloud environments.

See also updates on the following results in appendix A:

R6, R7, R8, R9 R10, R11, R12, R13, R14, R17

7.2 KPIs

Below, updates on the status of the KPIs are given.

Table 7.2: Update on KPIs

KPI2.1 - MIRTO transfers processes amongst at least 3 different processing/instruction set architectures for edge/fog/cloud nodes and is deployed and used in at least 2 cloud-edge scenarios outside the consortium.

The first version of the MIRTO cognitive engine modules and the MYRTUS Architecture (D3.1) are currently under implementation and integration. This first version will demonstrate orchestration of applications (and their processes) in all levels of the continuum (edge, fog, cloud). All the work carried out so far at the MIRTO cognitive engine level and WL orchestrators level is completely computing node agnostic. The only manager that is target specific, due to its goal in the Node Manager that is specifically conceived for FPGA-based edge nodes. Current work comprehends planned demonstrations at the two consortium use cases and using at least 2 different processing architectures: standard PCs and FPGA-based accelerated platforms.

KPI2.2 - Provide at least 20% improvements in all the considered applications' KPIs (as throughput, energy efficiency, processing and communication latency, network availability, bandwidth etc.) using MIRTO AI-powered strategies. Comparisons (simulations and testbed implementations) with/without the proposed strategies

The first version of the MIRTO cognitive engine modules and its integration (see KPI2.1) will include mechanisms to measure and monitor the target KPI's (throughput, energy efficiency, processing, and communication latency, network availability, and bandwidth). At the end of the first project phase, we expect to have these KPIs in measurement, whereas the analysis

of improvement in comparison with base testbeds and simulation will be part of the second project phase. Same holds for necessary adjustments in architecture and cognitive approaches (workload managers) to achieve the 20% goals.

KPI2.3 - Model and support at least 10 privacy preserving functions within MIRTO cognitive engine and deal with at least 3 types of restrictions (e.g., legal, geographical, or security) coming from the Gaia-X Framework.

The current version of P&S Manager supports 4 security and privacy functionalities, providing 3 different levels of security and implemented in different flavors. The S&P Manager is designed to support scalability, and other security and privacy functionalities can be easily added (as planned for the second phase of the project) The runtime support for security offered by the P&S Manager guarantees that the information security of applications keeps improving. Furthermore, the use of security and privacy preserving functions helps in achieving compliance by construction with related regulation.

7.3 Future work

As the project progresses, further enhancements and refinements will continually push the boundaries of dynamic and interoperable compute-continuum systems. The current focus of the project is on implementing and integrating this initial version. This implementation will enable each group to validate, assess, and refine their approaches in the subsequent project phase. Anticipated analyses and potential advancements during the following project phase include:

- Evaluation and fine-tuning of the overall structure, information model, and interfaces. Adjustments will reflect newly identified insights and requirements previously overlooked.
- Assessment and improvement of the Workload Managers:
 - The *DCOP WL Manager* requires evaluation regarding its runtime latency, as it relies on runtime simulations that may delay the orchestration process. Future developments may involve strategies (e.g., heuristics) to reduce the number of necessary simulations.
 - The *Swarm-based WL Manager* should be evaluated for scalability and refinement of swarm agents integration (Resource and Demand agents). This variant necessitates a substantial number of active MIRTO agents and intense communication among them. This aspect will be further refined and expanded in the second project phase.
 - The *DRL-based WL Manager* approach, which is based on distributed and federated reinforcement learning, will undergo assessment and validation. The specifics of the learning strategy are currently under investigation and should be solidified.
- The *Network Manager* will enhance the integration of network monitoring and control points.

- Similarly, the *Privacy & Security Manager* will refine security primitives' integration and control, expanding the quantity and variants of these primitives in the second project phase.
- Lastly, the *Node Manager* will continue developing the data-driven modelling approach for workload characterization and extend decision mechanisms for FPGA-based tasks.

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Appendices

Appendix A: Current status of pillar 2 results

R6	Model (AI and statistical) for WL characterization on edge technologies.
<p>Short Description: Approaches and methods for the characterization of the WLS, which encompass different techniques such as traditional statistical methods and ML-based models. These approaches will enable accurate both deployment-time and run-time estimations of different KPIs (e.g., execution latency/throughput, power/energy consumption). When possible, these models will support lifelong incremental learning to keep models up to date and consider unforeseen workload scenarios.</p>	
<p>Status update: Mechanisms for monitoring metrics related to execution time and power consumption of workloads that include FPGA-based hardware acceleration have been implemented. In addition, ML models focused on the FPGA platform have been validated, and statistical analysis based on metrics that take into account the various phases of workload orchestration management in the heterogeneous device at the edge is being defined.</p>	
R7	Chatbot WL implementation
<p>Short Description: Models based on LLM (Large Language Models) will be released, capable of receiving a specific workload as input (e.g., application, Docker, raw code) and producing an optimized version according to specific criteria (e.g., latency, security, energy consumption). The production of these models will begin with pre-trained models, utilising transfer learning techniques. The models will be specialized for the specific task through various fine-tuning techniques.</p>	
<p>Status update: A state-of-the-art context study has been carried out, and an implementation phase using fine-tuning techniques is planned from M19.</p>	
R8	Swarm-based orchestration algorithms
<p>Short Description: Library of swarm-based orchestration algorithms based on natural inspiration and evolutionary computation for dynamic 360° scheduling (horizontal and vertical) at edge-fog-cloud layer.</p>	

Status update: The library contains the ACO algorithm (see Appendix 3 for implementation and evaluation details) which was validated with different network settings and parameter configurations. The next step is the design and integration of a hormone-based swarm algorithm.

R9	Library of Multi-agent RL algorithms and hierarchical and asynchronous FL algorithms across cloud, fog, and edge
<p>Short Description: A cluster-based asynchronous FL framework is proposed to tackle the resource heterogeneity issue, which can be integrated in the MYRTUS system to enable the AI models used in the MIRTO Agent to evolve in a distributed manner.</p>	
<p>Status update: The overall framework of the proposed cluster-based asynchronous FL has been finished, it general includes multiple main algorithms to optimized the FL process, currently, we are working on the problem formulation of the first optimization problem as well as the algorithm.</p>	

R10	Dynamic Service Chains composition
<p>Short Description: Dynamic functional composition of Service Chains allows a MIRTO agent to instantiate different Service Chain configurations depending on the actual conditions and resource availability. The MIRTO agent will be able, for example, to dynamically decide and exchange between different service implementations -- given the implementations satisfy the requirements of other (user) services</p>	
<p>Status update: The dynamic Service Chain composition is currently in implementation as a feature in the DCOP workload manager. This feature enhances the DCOP workload manager optimization algorithm allowing the orchestration process to choose among different possible implementations of a service component (chain) during the orchestration. A demonstration of this feature using choices over a single Software Component is planned for month 18.</p>	

R11	OS-based manager for FPGA based edge devices
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Short Description:

OS-based and MIRTO-compatible manager to enable workload orchestration with standard interfaces (e.g., Kubernetes) but also providing low-level and node-specific resource management mechanisms to adapt the working point at run time (i.e., changing the configuration of the HMPSoCs or the RISC-V processor with custom CGRA-based extensions, which require different tuning knobs).

Status update:

OS-based support has been implemented in order to enable orchestration and monitoring of workload that include FPGA-based hardware acceleration.

R12	Network Manager
Short Description: The AI-enabled network manager will support the WL manager for estimating the transmission latency as well as the bandwidth allocation where DRL will be employed to decide the optimal bandwidth allocation.	
Status update: The functionality and the interface and the behaviour of the network manager has been defined. Currently, we are working on the DRL problem formulation of the bandwidth allocation.	

R13	Models of selected security and privacy primitives suitable for continuous monitoring.
Short Description: USI will generate models concerning several computational metrics of selected security and privacy primitives, such as symmetric encryption, authenticated encryption, homomorphic encryption, multi-party computation, and federated learning. The models will be based on open-source libraries suitable for continuous monitoring.	
Status update: The modules implementing symmetric encryption primitives have been constructed. Currently, we are working on the other security modules.	

R14	Virtual continuum library
Short Description: A set of libraries and tools designed to build a dynamic virtual continuum over fragmented	

cloud-edge infrastructures, enabling seamless scaling, optimized resource usage, and enhanced workload resilience.

Status update:

At project inception, Ligo was in a prototypal stage, with minimal functionality and loosely defined interfaces. Over the course of the current project phase, the library underwent substantial refactoring and stabilization. Interfaces were formalized, core features were hardened, and the codebase was modularized to support extensibility and better align with the architectural and integration requirements defined by the Myrthus project.

R17	SAM
<p>Short Description: SAM is a toolbox for solving Distributed Constraint Optimization Problems (DCOP), in MYRTUS this will be used by modelling the job/node resource allocation problem as a DCOP, using the outcome of DynAA (which is explained as part of Pillar 3, but it will be used at runtime too), allowing to use its algorithms at design-time and at runtime.</p>	
<p>Status update: The SAM toolbox already existed at the start of the project. In this first project period, the toolbox has been already matured, and enhanced for use as the core optimization solver for the orchestration process in the DCOP Workload manager. SAM is now an integral part of the DCOP workload manager. In the DCOP workload manager, SAM is tightly coupled to the DynAA simulation engine. DynAA provides scenario simulation (of the prospective application deployments) and respective KPI estimation. For the SAM-DynAA coupling, the following tasks were already accomplished:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Definition and implementation of an interface between the tools, allowing scenarios prospected by the DCOP workload manager to be described and transferred to DynAA. ● Translation of the scenario descriptions into (continuum) system simulations. ● Set of initial KPI analysis based on simulation traces. Initial focus is on cpu and memory utilization across the system. ● Reporting of KPI estimates back to the DCOP workload manager. Estimates are used by SAM to make orchestration decisions. 	

Appendix B: Glossary

Name	Description
Allocation Map	A list of all Software Component Allocations.
Compute Node	A component able to run a Software Component. E.g. a Linux Edge device, a Cloud computer, a virtual computer etc.
Distributed Knowledge Base	A central database containing blobs of information and/or files, that any component might need for persisting or sharing of knowledge.
Liqo	Liqo is an open-source project that enables Kubernetes clusters to share resources and workloads seamlessly. It allows for dynamic and secure multi-cluster environments, making it easier to manage and scale applications across different cloud providers or on-premises infrastructure.
MIRTO Agent	The core MIRTO service responsible for coordinating and accessing all MIRTO managers. Also the primary access point for the MIRTO software specialist for installing, monitoring and troubleshooting applications.
MIRTO Allocation	The linking of a Software Component with a Service Chain Component and a Compute Node.
MIRTO System Status	A data element representing the status of the MIRTO System.
MYRTUS System	The total of the MIRTO Hardware Infrastructure (consisting of Compute Nodes, and Network Nodes), the MIRTO Software Infrastructure (consisting of all MIRTO Services) and the MIRTO Application (consisting of all implementations of the Service Chain Components).
Network Node	A component representing a communication facility. For example a 5G Network Node, a WiFi Network Node, etc. When a Network Node is bound to 2 Compute Nodes, Software Components running on those Compute Nodes can exchange information with each other.
Orchestration	The process of defining MIRTO Allocations by linking i) Service Chain Components, ii) Software Component, and iii) Compute Nodes. The set of all MIRTO Allocations is called an Allocation Map.

Resource Registry	A specialized interface on top of the knowledge base to disseminate information on the status of the MYRTUS infrastructure.
Service Chain	A Service Chain is a network of Service Chain Components that represent specific tasks. For example, the Service Chain for the use case traffic safety warning consists amongst others of the Service Chain Components: Tracker, Multi-Sensor Merger, Map Matcher.
Service Chain Component	Basic component of a Service Chain. Represents a task to be executed. It can be realized by means of a Software Component.
Software Component	A basic service that realizes a Service Chain Component. Different alternatives for Service Chain Components exist where each Service Chain Component realizes the same ServiceChainComponent (e.g. one for the Cloud, one for the Fog, and one for the Edge).
TOSCA	Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications (TOSCA) is an open standard developed by the OASIS consortium. It aims to enhance the portability and management of cloud applications and services across different cloud environments.

Appendix C: Ant-Colony Algorithm for the Swarm-WL Manager

Swarm intelligence is a promising approach that provides adaptive methods for optimizing workload allocation in the edge-fog-cloud continuum, leveraging self-organization to efficiently manage distributed resources [Schranz-2021]. Rajesh et al. [Rajesh-2020] applied a swarm intelligence algorithm in IoT routing to extend network life and cut energy costs. Saba et al. [Saba-2023] proposed a load-balancing method using swarm intelligence for data management to reduce the response time of cloud servers. In another work, an innovative hybrid swarm intelligence algorithm was designed in [Attiya-2022] for task scheduling in cloud computing to increase the rate of convergence. The most innovative work comes from [Ghasemi-2024], where the authors tackle the dynamic nature of the available resources and workloads from the bottom-up. Delay-sensitive and insensitive pod agents are co-located in the modeled multi-agent system to minimize slack resources while improving resource utilization for edge micro data centers.

To tackle the high complexity behind workload allocation in the continuum, we implement the Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) based on the swarm behaviors of real ant colonies [Dorigo-2006]. Corominas-Murtra et al. [Corominas-2023] proposed an ACO-based method to deal with the network alignment issue. Wu et al. [Wu-2023] designed an adaptive ACO algorithm for path planning in robotics. In another work, the resource allocation problem was considered in [Du-2023] for avionics systems. They provided an improved ACO strategy to minimize the energy cost during the allocation task. Moreover, Chandrashekar et al. [Chandrashekar-2023] proposed a hybrid weight ACO method for task scheduling in cloud computing. This novel scheduler was able to enhance performance compared to some traditional algorithms. In summary, ACO is a powerful tool for optimization problems in network routing and scheduling [Bai-2024]. Thus, ACO seems to be a candidate algorithm for the flexible workload placement we require in the highly dynamic edge-fog-cloud continuum.

System Model

We introduce two types of swarm agents in the continuum: resource agents and demand agents. The resource agents are located in each computing node with available CPU and Memory (MEM) resources. They are embodied by a Multi-layer 360° dynamic RunTime Orchestration (MIRTO) engine, so we call them MIRTO agents. Thus, the MIRTO agents in the edge/fog/cloud computing paradigm are the MIRTO edge/fog/cloud agents (MEA/MFA/MCA). The type and capacity of the resources depend on their layer. Each MEA includes some IoT devices such as robots, smartphones, etc. MFA is comprised of a set of edge micro data centers (EMDC), and MCA is run by big servers with unlimited resource capacities. The demand agents are represented by pods in the Kuber-netes context. Each pod has a specific demand for resources and execution steps. So they are divided into small, medium, and large pods. Pods arrive in the continuum with specific steps generated by an exponential random variable with a parameter $\mu \in (0,1]$, which reveals the frequency of arriving pods.

The different resource agents are also connected to ensure that pods can move freely through the links. This enables all resource agents to jointly form a seamless edge-fog-cloud continuum.

Algorithm

We will introduce a swarm intelligence workload placement strategy inspired by the Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) algorithm, where we map the Service Chain Components to the role of ants that can release pheromones on each resource agent. Therefore, we define the pheromone

value on the resource agent v_i as τ_i . The initial pheromone value on each resource agent depends on the layer they are located at. We design the update scheme τ_i on the MIRTO agent v_i as

$$\tau_i := \tau_i + \gamma \Delta \tau_i^k$$

if the k^{th} pod finished execution on v_i . $\Delta \tau_i^k$ is the released pheromone value by pod k on v_i . This value is related to the demand of the k^{th} pod. γ is a parameter which represents the pheromone deposit factor.

In contrast, if the k^{th} pod arrives at v_i , but cannot be served here, we introduce the evaporation for the pheromone value on v_i . This can be regarded as the reduction of the pheromone value if the Service Chain Components are rejected to be served. The updated rule is designed as

$$\tau_i := (1 - \rho^k) \tau_i$$

where ρ^k denotes the evaporation rate which is also related to the demand of the k^{th} pod. Then, the pod should decide where to go next from the neighbor set \mathcal{N}_i . It can be observed from the above equations that the pheromone values reveal the available resources on each MIRTO agent.

When it comes to how to select the neighbors, we first implement two baseline algorithms (random and greedy). After that, we design a swarm intelligence algorithm for the selection based on the ACO method to make a decision for the next MIRTO agent from the set \mathcal{N}_i . The algorithms are presented as follows.

- Random: The Service Chain Components randomly choose a resource agent from the neighbor set \mathcal{N}_i and check the available resource again until they find the resource agent meeting their demand. Although the random algorithm exhibits excellent scalability, often requires less computational resources and can be easier to implement, it is hard to find the appropriate resource agent at an appropriate time in many cases.
- Greedy: The Service Chain Components move to a resource agent with the maximum pheromone value from the neighbor set \mathcal{N}_i (if there are multiple MIRTO agents with the same maximum pheromone value, one is randomly chosen). However, privacy issues may not be guaranteed since the Service Chain Components are inclined to go to the higher layer (edge to fog, or fog to cloud) under the greedy algorithm. Additionally, the inter-layer transmission cost is much higher than the intra-layer, which is not suitable for latency-sensitive tasks.
- ACO: As the transmission cost is also an important factor for workload management, it should be taken into consideration when Service Chain Components make their decision. Motivated by the ACO method, the Service Chain Components move to a resource agent $v_j \in \mathcal{N}_i$ with the probability p_j defined as follows

$$p_j = \frac{\tau_j^\alpha \eta_{ij}^\beta}{\sum_{v_j \in \mathcal{N}_i} \tau_j^\alpha \eta_{ij}^\beta}$$

where $\eta_{ij} = 1/c_{ij}$ denotes the heuristic desirability which is the inverse of the transmission cost between v_i and v_j .

α and β are two weighting parameters, one for the pheromone value, the other for the transmission cost. It can be observed from the above equation that Service Chain Components are favorable to move to the neighbor with a large number of available resources and low communication costs. Hence, more Service Chain Components can be served locally on the edge layer instead of moving to the fog or cloud layer. Algorithm 1 summarizes the behavior of Service Chain Components by implementing the ACO-based workload scheduling.

Figure XY illustrates three possible paths of a pod n with an exemplary demand of $D_n = (D^{CPU}_n, D^{MEM}_n) = (16, 16)$ to find the resource agent. The green path is generated under the random algorithm. Since the neighbor is selected randomly, the pod visits six MIRTO agents without enough available resources. Finally, it is transmitted to the cloud server. The blue path stands for the greedy algorithm, the pod moves directly to the MFA v_8 and then goes to the cloud server. The red one represents the most likely path of the pod under ACO algorithm. It can be served on fog layer without visiting too many MIRTO agents.

Figure 16 Conceptual scheme Swarming Workload management

Figure XY demonstrates an exemplary simulation result: the resource utilization (RU) on the edge layer. It compares a lightly loaded edge-fog-cloud continuum, configured with a pod arrival frequency of $\mu = 0.5$, to a heavily loaded continuum, where $\mu = 0.8$. The results show that the ACO algorithm achieves higher resource utilization on the edge layer compared to the two baseline algorithms. This indicates that, under both light and heavy load conditions, the ACO algorithm enables more Service Chain Components to be served locally, preventing them from migrating to higher layers.

Figure 17 Simulation results resource utilization edge layer.

Further system model definitions, simulation results and discussions can be found in the corresponding paper: Kefan Wu, Abdorasoul Ghasemi, and Melanie Schranz, Swarm Intelligence-Based Algorithm for Workload Placement in Edge-Fog-Cloud Continuum, In Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on Agents and Artificial Intelligence (ICAART 2025), pages 310-317, 2025⁶.

⁶ <https://www.scitepress.org/Papers/2025/131408/131408.pdf>

Appendix D: DCOP problem formulation for the Workload Manager

Distributed Constraint Optimization Problems (DCOPs) are problems formulated as a tuple of Agents, Variables, Domains and Constraints. All agents are assigned a variable, which they have to cooperatively assign a value, by negotiating with other agents [Hirayama-1997, Grinshpoun-2013]. Constraint costs are the penalties or costs incurred when constrained variables are assigned some values. DCOPs are generic mathematical descriptions of problems, and can apply to many different domains, therefore, a problem mapping must be made that describes the workload management problem in terms of DCOPs.

In order to do this we have to define the different choices that have to be made in terms of **variables**, the values to choose from for each variable as the corresponding **domains**. The entities that have to decide which values to assign are called **agents**, and are the entities where some logic can be executed in the form of an algorithm. Moreover, in DCOPs, agents can communicate with one another, in order to coordinate their decision making. Finally, we have to specify how good or bad a certain set of allocations is by defining the cost functions. In a DCOP this is done by specifying relations between variables, which are referred to as **constraints**. These four components: variables, domains, agents and constraints, define the DCOP, and for the workload manager we use the following components, where there are two *types* of variables and corresponding domains, and two *types* of constraints between variables.

- **Service implementation variables:** For every Service Chain Component there is one service implementation variable for selecting a suitable Software Component implementation. This variable indicates that for each Service Chain Components, exactly one fitting implementation must be selected. By definition, assigning a value to this variable is equivalent to deciding which Software Component will be selected for a Service Chain Component. This means, for instance, that if there are multiple algorithms for a vehicle tracking Service Chain Component, this variable indicates that a choice has to be made for the actual “vehicle tracking” service component.
 - **Service implementation domains:** The corresponding domains from which the agents can choose are the implementing Software Components for a given Service Component. If there is only a single potential implementing Software Component this domain has a size of exactly one, and the variable is not really a variable and may be omitted from the problem definition. In cases where there are more than one potential Software Components, this domain is equal to the set to choose from. In the same example as before, the domain is the set of vehicle tracking implementations or algorithms to choose from.
- **Service allocation variables:** In addition to the previous type of variable, every Service Chain Component has exactly one allocation variable. This variable specifies that for every Service Chain Component, a Compute Node must be found that will execute it. Equivalently, assigning a value to this variable corresponds to assigning a Compute Node to a Service Chain Component. In the vehicle tracker example, this variable indicates the choice that has to be made on which compute node the tracker will run.
 - **Service allocation domains:** The service allocation domains are the available Compute Nodes that can run a Service Component. Notice that Compute Nodes are assigned to Service Chain Components and not the other way around. By using the Compute Nodes as domains, it is guaranteed that for each Service Component, exactly one Compute Node is selected.

- **Agents:** The DCOP agents that make the decisions on value assignment are virtual agents that run inside the workload manager, representing a single service implementation or service implementation. The assumption is made that each agent is responsible for exactly one variable. This is not a strict necessity in a DCOP, but for practicality, in nearly all use cases this assumption is made.
- **Compute resource constraints (allocation vs. implementation):** A constraint for every Service Component exists between the implementation and allocation variable. This constraint implies the cost of an implementation on a specific Compute Node. This can be a hard constraint which specifies whether the implementation is even possible, or it can be a soft constraint that determines the system load of that Compute Node and how much additional load an implementation will give.
- **Network resource constraints (allocation vs. allocation):** Additionally, a constraint exists between one allocation variable and another allocation variable, provided that service components need to communicate with one another. Mapping two services on the same or on different Compute Modes will yield additional load on the network. This relation will be described in a soft constraint that determines the latency of two communicating services.

The biggest asset of modelling a problem as a DCOP, is that it allows to express the dependencies between two or more choices. If one choice influences another, this means there is some constraint between two variables. Using this way of modelling the problem means that a problem graph can be constructed, showing all dependent choices. A small problem of three communicating Service Chain Components is visually depicted in Figure 18. In the figure the vertices (circles) represent service implementation variables (s_i) and service allocations variables (s_a). Edges (lines) between the vertices are the constraints, where connected vertices represent dependencies between different variable assignments. The problem graph shows that choices of one service allocation affects other service allocations, but service implementations are only affected by their corresponding allocation variables. This means the problem graph is connected, but not fully connected. This means it is feasible and computationally effective to solve as a DCOP.

Figure 18 An example DCOP problem graph showing dependencies between 3 allocation variables, and 3 implementation variables.

When the problem is converted to a DCOP formulation, the SAM DCOP library will be used to find solutions that minimize the sum of all constraints.

There are many different algorithms that are able to solve DCOPs, which one method will need to be selected from. In order to do that, we can compare different solvers using different characteristics. One very important characteristic is whether the algorithm is *complete*, meaning it is guaranteed to find the global optimum. Some examples of *complete* solvers are AFB [Gershman-2009] or DPOP [Petcu-2005]. Alternatively, an algorithm might be *incomplete*, which means it does some trade-off for computational effectiveness vs. solution cost. Some incomplete solvers include DSA [Fitzpatrick-2003] or MGM-2 [Maheswaran-2004]. Since the problem in general is known to be NP-hard [Modi-2003], the computational resources required for complete solvers, by definition, grow exponentially with the problem size. For this reason we will mainly focus on incomplete solvers.

Another distinguishing characteristic of DCOP solvers is whether they allow for *asymmetric* constraints [Grinshpoun-2013]. Asymmetric constraints are constraints where a certain variable allocation has a different cost for one agent than for another. To give an example of such asymmetric constraints: in our traffic use case, placing the vehicle tracking Software Component on a fog node may be beneficial for the agent responsible for the vehicle tracking, but is detrimental for the agent that controls the sensor merging Software Component. It is actually possible to convert an asymmetric constraint into a symmetric constraint, but taking not the individual costs, but instead only the sum of the cost, but this has a privacy aspect. It means that the agent will have to know about the (potentially sensitive) cost information about *all* value assignments of its connected neighbors. For this reason we will limit our search for solvers that can natively deal with asymmetric constraints.

Solvers that are able to solve asymmetric DCOPs are for instance ACLS [Grinshpoun-2013] or GCA-MGM [Grubstein-2010] and to a certain extent Max-sum [Zivan-2015]. All of these solvers have in common that they have an “iterative” approach. This means that they all start out with a random assignment for their variables, and have agents communicate with one another to update their assignments until a solution is found that is at least locally optimal. A different approach is used by the CoCoA algorithm [vanLeeuwen-2017], which instead uses a non-iterative approach that has agents communicate even before they select a random value. This generally results in a very fast convergence, and when used as a starting point for further fine tuning with an iterative solver, in lower solution costs [vanLeeuwen-2018]. This is why for the WLM the CoCoA algorithm will be used to select a starting point, potentially improving it with another algorithm with low communication overhead, such as ACLS.

